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Parallel Dynamic Mode Decomposition

Identifying spatiotemporal patterns with HPC

Bachelorarbeit von

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Eigenständigkeitserklärung

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1 Motivation

The complexity of problems faced in many practical applications, inter alia occurring in natural, physical and engineering science, is increasingly prevalent. However, until this very day, there exists no fully developed theory for grand challenges such as climate (change), disease modeling or the unraveling of all functionalities of the human brain. In an analogous manner, an economist cannot rely on an exact formula, though might aspire to benefit from stock market predictions either way, as would an engineer pondering about turbulence control or the combustion of a rocket.

One may remark, that despite the partly extensively varying context, these topicalities all may be classified as high-dimensional phenomena which evolve (nonlinearly) in time. Such, however, are typically confronted with one grand challenge: they are (yet) too complex to be understood by a first principles approach, as originally common throughout the last centuries of science. However, with the rise of memory capacities, processor frequencies and further developed technology in general, the era of *Big Data* introduces another strategy to be considered: The concept of *data-driven techniques*.

Thus, instead of formulating complete theorems first, it is their paradigm to extract the most dominant system dynamics *directly* from the corresponding data. Irrespective of their originating context, given e.g. by an experiment, historical record or numerical simulation, they offer plenty of potential for various applications. I.e., among others: the prediction of a future state, the optimization of design (such as a rocket or airplane), actuation, or control of a system and last but not least the interpretability of the obtained results, leading one back to the benefits for science [3, 14].

However, though tempting in theory, one must be particularly aware of one challenge coming along with inflating data amounts, i.e. the growth of execution time. Thus, to overcome this obstacle and fully capitalize the benefits of Big Data, one may exploit optimization techniques of *High Performance Computing* (HPC).

The conflation of both, with the concrete example of the *Dynamic Mode Decomposition* will be further discussed in the upcoming work.

2 Foundational matters

2.1 Dynamical systems

Before one dives deeper into a subject, it is crucial to grasp the context on which one operates. In the case of the *Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD)*, this is namely given by the field of differential equations, or in other words, *dynamical systems*.

Theorem 1 (Continuous-time dynamical system). *A differential equation of the form*

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{d}{dt}\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t), t, \boldsymbol{\beta}) \quad (2.1)$$

*will from now on be referred to as a (**continuous-time**) dynamical system, or **flow** where \mathbf{f} denotes the vector field, possibly depending on \mathbf{x} , the state of the system, as well as the time t and the remaining parameters captured in $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ ¹.*

We may also interpret t as an additional parameter hence obtaining the

Definition 1. *Autonomous system*

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t), \boldsymbol{\beta}) \quad (2.2)$$

which one may even further simplify to

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (2.3)$$

in order to increase the readability of the equation. As every system may be transformed into an autonomous system, we will restrict our analysis to such within this thesis without loss of generality.

However, though all parameters may be integrated in the state vector \mathbf{x} with ease, it is redundant to say, that the underlying semantics of each component remain unchanged.

¹Throughout this thesis, the bold notation indicates possibly multidimensional vectors, which may only in the rarest occasions considered to be scalar

The state is often assumed to be a simple vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, whereas \mathbf{f} represents a Lipschitz continuous function, hence ensuring the uniqueness and existence of the underlying solutions.

As evident, this definition depends on the differentiability of the system. However, one may easily obtain a discretized version given as

Theorem 2 (Autonomous discrete-time dynamical system). *An autonomous discrete-time dynamical system is defined as*

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{x}(t_k + t) = \mathbf{F}_t(\mathbf{x}_k) = \mathbf{x}_k + \int_{t_k}^{t_k+t} \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(\tau)) \mathbf{d}\tau \quad (2.4)$$

where the evolution, or (flow) map \mathbf{F}_t advances the state vector \mathbf{x}_k given at time t_k one time step t ². Hence, one obtains the state at time $t_{k+1} = t_k + t$ which is given by \mathbf{x}_{k+1} .³

The second form is more commonly present in practice, as the discretization might correspond to measurements taken throughout different time intervals t within an experimental setup. Within this thesis, we only approach equidistant discretizations, even though this is not mandatory within the DMD context (cf. [3, 14]).

Additionally, one must also note that in spite of the topicality of the subject, a bunch of challenges comes along with dynamical systems. First, there is the matter of

Uncertainty This aspect is prevalent in every component of this analysis (and presumably relies in the nature of research itself). In the worst case, which is unfortunately most common, the observed governing equations captured in \mathbf{f} are unknown. This sense of uncertainty trivially also applies to the additional parameters β , as well as the elements of the state \mathbf{x} themselves. And even if one would be certain of every component, another problem arises, i.e. the

High-Dimensionality of the data and resulting model. Thus, to achieve interpretability and meaningful insight into a system, one has to derive so called *Reduced Order Models* (ROMs), which aim to reflect the core behaviour of the system. For instance, this may be achieved by projecting the data into a basis capturing the most prevalent coherent spatiotemporal patterns. Concrete strategies of how to find them in a sophisticated manner, will be discussed in the upcoming chapters.

Ahead, one must mention one of the core obstacles to defy, i.e., the

²the discretization is hereby assumed to be equidistant

³The dependence on other parameters, equivalent to 2.1, is omitted for similar reasons

Nonlinearity of a system. What may not seem obvious to practitioners outside the field, is actually a large issue within the community. The reason for this is that in contrast to the opposing linear systems, in general no exact theory for their solution can be derived. Furthermore, they exhibit the risk of chaos, leading to sole probabilistic assertions as of a specific point. In such chaotic systems, rather small modifications in the input configuration might lead to extensively varying behaviour in the resulting output. This is also known as a *bifurcation*. An example of such, is depicted in figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Bifurcation diagram of a chaotic system on the example of the logistic map represented by the recurrence relation $x_{k+1} = \beta x_k(1 - x_k)$ with the corresponding flow map $x(t) = \mathbf{F}_t(\mathbf{x}_0) = \beta x_0(1 - x_0)$ [3]. It is evident, that for some configurations in β , prediction equals probability. Precisely, one observes a bifurcation for $\beta \approx 3$, another at $\beta \approx 3.45$ and as of $\beta \approx 3.55$ pure chaos may be observed.

All of the stated aspects constitute only a small fraction of the defiances coming along with the analysis of dynamical systems. However, within this thesis, we aim to unravel them as refined as we may. Starting off with nonlinearity, we may approach its counterpart in order to get a deeper insight into the desired specificities.

One of the most important, as already indicated, is that only such offer the potential of closed-form solutions including all associated advantages. A fraction of them will be further elaborated in the following.

2.2 Linear systems

2.2.1 Phase space and stability

Theorem 3 (Linear dynamical system). *A linear dynamical system is given by*

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} \quad (2.5)$$

where the solution, uniquely determined by an initial condition $\mathbf{x}(t_0) = \mathbf{x}_0$ is obtained as

$$\mathbf{x}(t_0 + t) = e^{\mathbf{A}t} \mathbf{x}_0 \quad (2.6)$$

Apart from the intriguing simplicity of such closed-up form, linearity inhabits the potential of plain interpretable results. Given that \mathbf{A} is constant, the dynamics of the system are characterized by the spectrum of its coefficient matrix.

We will further analyze them by visualizing exemplary *phase portraits*. Such constructs displays all *trajectories/ orbits/ solution curves* $\{\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n | t \in T\}$ within the *phase*⁴ *space* of a system. Such is spanned by the different input coordinate axes, whilst T is a representant of the considered time interval. On top of that, we scrutinize some particular points of interest given as the so called *equilibrium points*.

Definition 2. Any point $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$, that satisfies $\mathbf{f}(t, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}) = \dot{\mathbf{x}} = 0$ is called an *equilibrium or critical point*.

One may remark, that for the linear case, the set of all equilibrium points is given by $\ker(A)$. From a physical point of view, the information encoded may be interpreted as a uniform motion. Thus, given a system where the initial value equals the equilibrium point, the trajectory will remain in place $\forall t$ ⁵. For this reason, the set is also referred to as the *steady state solution* [16].

However, given the practical context, one would be particularly interested in the stability of the close environment of such points, thus, the influence of small perturbations on the general system dynamics. For instance, one often aims to analyze the *attractors*, which comprise a state reached for $t \rightarrow \infty$ and the corresponding *attractor basins*, thus the range within which the trajectories behave stable hence converge against a fixed point.

Driven by this ambition, we will attain a visualization of the most crucial scenarios by means of some 2×2 examples. Each configuration will be considered separately.

CASE 1 - Same sign real distinct eigenvalues ($\lambda_{1,2} \in \mathbb{R} \neq 0 \wedge \text{sign}(\lambda_1) = \text{sign}(\lambda_2)$) The solution is given by

$$\mathbf{x} = c_1 \mathbf{v}_1 e^{\lambda_1 t} + c_2 \mathbf{v}_2 e^{\lambda_2 t}$$

One may remark, that for $t \rightarrow \infty$ two different scenarios might occur, depending on the sign of the eigenvalues. If $\text{sign}(\lambda_i) < 0$, the trajectories converge

⁴The term “phase“ originates from mechanics and Newton’s second law, encoding the motion of a particle as $m \ddot{\mathbf{x}} + \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}, \dot{\mathbf{x}}) = 0$ s.t. \mathbf{x} , $\dot{\mathbf{x}}$ define the position, velocity, respectively. In our context, “phase“ generalizes to the state components [16]

⁵under the assumption of no energy supply

towards the origin, otherwise, they diverge. This behaviour is reflected in figure 2.2. The resulting equilibrium point is called *sink*, *source* respectively. As one may already assume, the first case exhibits *asymptotic stability*, whereas the second corresponds to an *unstable* point in the system.

Figure 2.2: Phase portrait of Case 1. The left phase portrait depicts a *node* or (*nodal*) *sink* as its critical point, the right a (*nodal*) *source* [12]

CASE 2 - Different sign real distinct eigenvalues ($\lambda_{1,2} \in \mathbb{R} \neq 0 \wedge \text{sign}(\lambda_1) \neq \text{sign}(\lambda_2)$) Similarly to the previous case, one encounters phenomenoms of con- and divergence depending on the sign of the eigenvalue. As in one direction divergence is observed, the hereby appearing *saddle point* is classified *unstable*.

Figure 2.3: Phase portrait of Case 2. A *saddle point* is represented [12].

Approaching the complex case, let

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda & -\mu \\ \mu & \lambda \end{bmatrix}$$

such that with the consideration of Euler's formula

$$e^{i\lambda t} = \cos(\lambda t) + i \sin(\lambda t) \tag{2.7}$$

the solution is given by

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \underbrace{e^{\lambda t}}_a \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \cos(\mu t) & -\sin(\mu t) \\ \sin(\mu t) & \cos(\mu t) \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{C}} \mathbf{x}_0$$

It is evident, that some periodic shares influence the system dynamics. Note that \mathbf{C} is unitary, denoting a rotation around the equilibrium point, where the direction is determined by the sign of μ .

CASE 3 - Complex distinct eigenvalues with zero real part ($\lambda_{1,2} \in \mathbb{C}$, $Re(\lambda_{1,2}) = 0$) As $a = e^{\lambda t} = 1$ the trajectories denote a circle in the phase space. Its radius is hereby determined by the initial value as $|\mathbf{x}(t)| = |\mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}_0| \stackrel{\mathbf{C} \text{ unitary}}{=} |\mathbf{x}_0|$. This equilibrium point, a *center* behaves *stable*.

Figure 2.4: Phase portrait of Case 3. For $\mu < 0$, the trajectories orbit clockwise, for $\mu > 0$ counter-clockwise around the *center* [12].

CASE 4 - Complex distinct eigenvalues with non-zero real part ($\lambda_{1,2} \in \mathbb{C}$, $Re(\lambda_{1,2}) \neq 0$) In this case $a = e^{\lambda t} \neq 1$, thus, alongside its evolution, the amplitude of the trajectory changes (i.e. grows/ decays depending on whether $\lambda < 0$ or $\lambda > 0$) with time. Consequently, it winds around the *focus* or *spiral sink/source*, which is classified as *asymptotically stable*, *unstable* respectively.

Figure 2.5: Phase portrait of Case 4. This phase portrait depicts a *focus* [12]

The degenerate case won't be further elaborated within this thesis, as sufficient intuition has been established already [2, 12, 16].

2.2.2 Spectral representation of regular operators

Apart from the benefits of such, one may also exploit the spectral decomposition

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Lambda} \quad (2.8)$$

to retrieve a particularly sophisticated solution to the original problem stated in Theorem 3.

Apart from the trivial constraint that \mathbf{A} must be quadratic ($n \times n$), we require it to be self-adjoint at first.

Corollary 3.1 ((Self-)adjoint). \mathbf{A}^* defines the adjoint (operator) of \mathbf{A} if

$$\langle \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} \rangle = \langle \mathbf{A}^*\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x} \rangle \quad (2.9)$$

with respect to a specific inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ ⁶ If $\mathbf{A}^* = \mathbf{A}$, the operator is said to be self-adjoint, or Hermitian. Consequently

$$\langle \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} \rangle = \langle \mathbf{A}\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x} \rangle = \langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{A}\mathbf{y} \rangle \quad (2.10)$$

In the finite-dimensional context, the adjoint is generally given by the complex conjugate transposed, which reduces to the transpose in the real case. Hence, under these restrictions, Hermitian is equivalent to $\mathbf{A}^* = \mathbf{A}^T$ i.e. the symmetric property.

Under these constraints, which furthermore state that we obtain n real distinct eigenvalues determined as the diagonal entries of $\mathbf{\Lambda}$, we can conclude that the corresponding (right) eigenvectors \mathbf{v}_k captured in the columns of \mathbf{V} form an orthonormal⁷ basis set for the complete domain of \mathbf{A} . Hence, any vector (including our solution) \mathbf{x} may be represented within that basis of (right) eigenvectors as

$$\mathbf{x} = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k \mathbf{v}_k \quad (2.11)$$

as may the effect of

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k \lambda_k \mathbf{v}_k \quad (2.12)$$

⁶which may be arbitrary chosen, though for vectors we will define $\mathbf{x}^*\mathbf{x}$

⁷If not already, the eigenvectors may be easily normalized. Mutual orthogonality is guaranteed.

since the eigenvectors are by construction chosen to be invariant under the application of the operator.

Due to the orthonormality of the basis set, the coefficients are determined by

$$\alpha_k = \langle \mathbf{v}_k, \mathbf{x} \rangle \quad (2.13)$$

hence the orthogonal projection onto the set of orthonormal eigenvectors. Equation 2.12 defines the desired *spectral representation* of \mathbf{A} which we may now capitalize to simplify the linear system of equations

$$\mathbf{Ax} = \mathbf{b} \quad (2.14)$$

where we herewith define the coefficients determining the projection of \mathbf{b} onto the span of eigenvectors as β_k analogously to 2.11.

Hence equation 2.14 becomes equivalent to

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k \lambda_k \mathbf{v}_k = \sum_{k=1}^n \beta_k \mathbf{v}_k \quad (2.15)$$

and we may dissolve the equation to derive

$$\alpha_k = \frac{\beta_k}{\lambda_k} \quad (2.16)$$

completing the formula of our solution as

$$\mathbf{x} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\beta_k}{\lambda_k} \mathbf{v}_k, \quad \beta_k = \langle \mathbf{v}_k, \mathbf{b} \rangle \quad (2.17)$$

Notice, that due to the Hermitian property, we have relied on various simplifications.

First and foremost, we could conclude the completeness of the set of eigenvectors, which is equivalent to the existence of n real and distinct eigenvalues. In general, especially in the case of *repeated*⁸ eigenvalues, the justification of this assumption can no longer be upheld. In such case, it is not sufficient to work with (right) eigenvectors alone, but required to take other concepts, such as the *Jordan canonical form* and the *generalized eigenvectors* into account. However, such will not be discussed any further within this thesis (for more information cf. [9]). Instead, though omitting the Hermitian property, we will from now on assume a *simple* operator, hence a complete basis set of eigenvectors, meaning that every eigenvector has rank one and the coordinate system spans the whole space.

Nevertheless, we can no longer assume, that the eigenvectors are mutually orthogonal, hence destroying the simplifications essential to equation 2.27. As

⁸meaning that their algebraic multiplicity is larger than 1

a result, we aim to attain a similar decoupled representation within a different coordinate system.

By means of that, we may formulate the eigenproblem for the adjoint operator as

$$\mathbf{A}^* \tilde{\mathbf{V}} = \tilde{\mathbf{V}} \tilde{\Lambda} \quad (2.18)$$

which again introduces the representation of any vector \mathbf{y} in the spanned space as

$$\mathbf{y} = \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_k \quad (2.19)$$

and the entire spectral representation of \mathbf{A}^* as

$$\mathbf{A}^* \mathbf{y} = \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \lambda_k^* \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_k \quad (2.20)$$

Fortunately, the orthogonality may be easily proven since under the restriction that $\lambda \neq \lambda^*$

$$\lambda \langle \mathbf{v}_k, \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_k \rangle = \langle \mathbf{A} \mathbf{v}_k, \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_k \rangle = \langle \mathbf{v}_k, \mathbf{A}^* \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_k \rangle = \langle \mathbf{v}_k, \tilde{\lambda}_k \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_k \rangle = \tilde{\lambda}_k^* \langle \mathbf{v}_k, \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_k \rangle \quad (2.21)$$

is equivalent to

$$(\lambda_k - \tilde{\lambda}_k^*) \langle \mathbf{v}_k, \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_k \rangle = 0 \quad (2.22)$$

which implies, the mutual orthogonality of the two basis sets (and naturally their entire span). Consequently, once again under the assumption of normalized basis vectors, we may state

$$\langle \mathbf{v}_j, \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_k \rangle = \delta_{jk} = \begin{cases} 1, & j = k \\ 0, & j \neq k \end{cases} \quad (2.23)$$

This completes our observations for Hermitian systems, in which the set of the right is identical to the set of left eigenvectors (as row and column space are identical), hence orthogonality can be trivially applied.

Analogously to the self-adjoint case, we may continue to derive the coefficients α_k, γ_k of the two induced coordinate systems, by means of an orthogonal projection into the space, which provides an orthogonal basis set, hence

$$\alpha_k = \langle \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_k, \mathbf{x} \rangle \quad (2.24)$$

$$\gamma_k = \langle \mathbf{v}_k, \mathbf{y} \rangle \quad (2.25)$$

[11, 25]. Capitalizing this insight in order to achieve a diagonal system representation, we project the solution into the basis of the adjoint eigenvectors

followed by some transformations under the exploitation of orthonormality, such that

$$\langle \mathbf{b}, \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_j \rangle = \langle \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}, \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_j \rangle = \langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{A}^* \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_j \rangle = \tilde{\lambda}_j^* \left\langle \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k \mathbf{v}_k, \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_j \right\rangle = \tilde{\lambda}_j^* \alpha_j$$

to consequently derive the closed-up formula for the coefficients

$$\alpha_k = \frac{\langle \mathbf{b}, \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_k \rangle}{\tilde{\lambda}_k^*} \quad (2.26)$$

and plug it into the solution as

$$\mathbf{x} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\beta_k}{\tilde{\lambda}_k^*} \mathbf{v}_k, \quad \beta_k = \langle \mathbf{b}, \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_k \rangle \quad (2.27)$$

[9, 14] One may take a moment to ponder *what* we have actually done here and *why* we have done it.

First, notice that both solution formula 2.17 and 2.27 may be interpreted as a different representation of $\mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{b}$. Hence, one may conclude that the first benefit of such derivation is the omitted concrete computation of the matrix inverse, which may be computationally expensive. On the other hand, one may fairly admit, that the eigenproblem is presumably not solved in noteworthy smaller costs.

So, to fully grasp the benefit of a solution within the basis of eigenvectors, one must recall the context on which one operates, i.e. a (*linear*) *dynamical system* as stated at the very beginning of this chapter. Hence, instead of one static solution \mathbf{b} , what we are mainly interested in, is the *evolution* of such system in time.

Fortunately, we have already derived a formula encoding such behaviour, captured in equation 2.6. However, the question about the concrete advantage of a spectral representation remains. To demonstrate the coherence of these two aspects, one may first recall that the exponential is nothing else than the Taylor series

$$e^x = \sum_0^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n!} \quad (2.28)$$

Hence, if we just plug in the system matrix \mathbf{A} we obtain

$$e^{\mathbf{A}t} = I + \mathbf{A}t + \frac{(\mathbf{A}t)^2}{2} + \frac{(\mathbf{A}t)^3}{6} + \dots + \frac{(\mathbf{A}t)^n}{n!} + \dots \quad (2.29)$$

which may be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned}
e^{\mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{V}^{-1}t} &= I + \mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{V}^{-1}t + \frac{(\mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{V}^{-1}t)^2}{2} + \dots + \frac{(\mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{V}^{-1}t)^n}{n!} + \dots \\
&= \mathbf{V}\mathbf{V}^{-1} + \mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{V}^{-1}t + \frac{(\mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{V}^{-1}t)^2}{2} + \dots + \frac{(\mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{V}^{-1}t)^n}{n!} + \dots \\
&= \mathbf{V}e^{\mathbf{\Lambda}t}\mathbf{V}^{-1} = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{E}(t)\mathbf{V}^{-1}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.30}$$

where

$$\mathbf{E}(t) = \text{diag}(e^{\lambda_1 t}, e^{\lambda_2 t}, \dots, e^{\lambda_n t}) \tag{2.31}$$

As a result, our solution is given as

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{V}e^{\mathbf{\Lambda}t}\mathbf{V}^{-1}\mathbf{x}_0 \tag{2.32}$$

One may pay particular attention on the meaning behind this equation. Precisely, one may state, that within the space of the (adjoint) eigenvectors, our system dynamics become *decoupled*, hence allowing an effortless derivation of the fundamental and resulting general solution(s) [9, 23].

This will be demonstrated in the course of a concrete example provided by [12]. For instance, given the linear system

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{x}_1 &= -x_1 - 3x_2 \\
\dot{x}_2 &= 2x_2
\end{aligned}$$

equivalently formulated in matrix form

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 3 \\ 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

inhabits the eigenvectors

$$\mathbf{v}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{v}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

inducing the orthogonal transformations

$$\mathbf{V} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{V}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

which result in a diagonal matrix, revealing the eigenvalues $\lambda_1 = -1$, $\lambda_2 = 2$ as

$$\mathbf{V}^{-1}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{V} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

This may be additionally verified after the extraction of the system of differential equations under the space of $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{V}^{-1}\mathbf{x}$ as

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{y}_1 &= -y_1 \\ \dot{y}_2 &= 2y_2\end{aligned}$$

which makes it clear that the variables are indeed decoupled. Following equation 2.32, the solution is easily derived as

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{V} \begin{bmatrix} e^{-t} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{2t} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{V}^{-1}\mathbf{x}_0$$

Even further, one may exploit such projection by recalling how each system state could be constructed. That is, the repeated application of the system matrix, which is mathematically encoded by the power of \mathbf{A} . Hence, in the discrete case of a recurrence relation

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_k \tag{2.33}$$

we obtain analogously

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{A}^{k-1}\mathbf{x}_0 = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Lambda}^{k-1}\mathbf{V}^{-1}\mathbf{x}_0 \tag{2.34}$$

[9].

Apart from that, one may note that provided with this theory, we are able to fully capitalize the results of subsection 2.2.1. Hence, depending on the value of the real part of each eigenvalue, we may predict, or at least get a solid first intention, of how exactly the system will evolve without even calculating it specifically. For instance, in the case of asymptotic stability ($Re(\lambda) < 0$), we may identify the attractor as the projection on the eigenvector corresponding to $\lambda = 0$.

The list could be continued with ease, though it may have become evident already, that a lot of desirable features come along with the attribute of linearity. Thus, it is straightforward to ponder about a method of capitalizing such specificity in spite of a highly nonlinear world, which - one may remark - is also the main motivation for the DMD. An approach to this challenge is given by the subject of the following chapter, the *Koopman Analysis*.

2.3 Koopman Analysis

Every of the above stated aspects is based on the point of view represented by various mathematicians and physicians, inter alia Henri Poincaré or Alexander Ljapunov at the end of the 19th century. They classified dynamical systems

into states, which may be straight-forward taking an experimental setup or e.g. observations in celestial mechanics into account. Inter alia in this field, on the specific example of the well-known three-body problem, Poincaré was considered a pioneer [17]. Though conferring a doctorate on the same subject under George Birkhoff, Bernard O. Koopman introduced yet another perspective in his paper published decades later in 1931 [13].

Instead of thinking about a finite-dimensional state space, he considered the infinite-dimensional space of scalar measurement functions

$$g_i(x_j) : \mathbb{C} \mapsto \mathbb{C} \quad (2.35)$$

which one could possibly apply to the components x_j of the state input \mathbf{x} . These could constitute every imaginable function that satisfies such restriction, may it be $\sin(x_j)$, $\cos(x_j)$ or something more complex such as $\sqrt[13]{\arctan(e^{42x_j}\pi)}$. This infinite set of possible choices, also called *observables*, may then be stacked into a single vector

$$\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) : \mathbb{C}^n \mapsto \mathbb{C}^\infty \quad (2.36)$$

which we may name the *operator of observables*.

The resulting state instance in the Hilbert space at one concrete point in time, will be denoted as \mathbf{y} in the same manner as \mathbf{x} in the finite vector space. We will refer to it as the *state of observables*.

Having derived all definitions, one may already assume, that a random choice of the operator of observables \mathbf{g} might be rather fruitful. Instead, one must recall the crux of his concept. That is, the projection of the data in such a manner, that the original non-linear system in the finite-dimensional state space behaves linearly in the infinite Hilbert space of measurements \mathcal{H} . The derivation of such function space is highly non-trivial, though will be discussed at a later point within this thesis. Instead, we will further analyze the linear operator that realizes such mapping, which is known as the *Koopman operator* \mathcal{K}_t .

Theorem 4 (Koopman operator). *The linear-infinite dimensional Koopman operator $\mathcal{K}_t : \mathbb{C}^\infty \mapsto \mathbb{C}^\infty$ (sometimes also referred to as composition operator) is defined in the following way:*

$$\mathcal{K}_t \mathbf{g} = \mathbf{g} \circ \mathbf{F}_t$$

such that it advances a state vector \mathbf{x}_k in the given space of measurement functions, respectively the state of observables \mathbf{y} itself one time step t forward, i.e.

$$\mathcal{K}_t \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}_k) = \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{F}_t(\mathbf{x}_k)) = \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}_{k+1})$$

Figure 2.6: Figure illustrating the concept of the Koopman expansion [4]. The operator of observables \mathbf{g} maps the finite state \mathbf{x} to the state of observables \mathbf{y} spanned within a potentially infinite-dimensional space \mathcal{H} of measurement functions g_i . The Koopman operator \mathcal{K}_t advances the state of observables \mathbf{y}_k *linearly*, the flow map \mathbf{F}_t the state \mathbf{x} (potentially non-linearly) forward in time.

The concept is schematically outlined within figure 2.6.

In sum, one may fairly admit, that one trades dimensionality with linearity. What might not seem like a good exchange at first - and for sure is not in all cases - one may emphasize some of the core benefits. The first, as one might already assume, is the advantage of an existing solution theory which may be easily adapted from the previous statements.

Hence, we one once again consider an eigenproblem

$$\mathcal{K}_t \varphi_k = \lambda_k \varphi_k \quad (2.37)$$

where hereby φ_k denotes the k^{th} *eigenfunction* in the Hilbert space spanned by the observables.

Subsequently, analogously to the state, one may rewrite the scalar measurement functions g_i within the basis of eigenfunctions as

$$g_i(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \varphi_j(\mathbf{x}) v_{ij} \quad (2.38)$$

such that one may consequently denote the state of observables \mathbf{g} as a whole as the linear combination of eigenfunctions φ_k with the corresponding weighting *Koopman modes* \mathbf{v}_k given as

$$\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{bmatrix} g_1(\mathbf{x}) \\ g_2(\mathbf{x}) \\ \vdots \\ g_p(\mathbf{x}) \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \varphi_k(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{v}_k \quad (2.39)$$

Furthermore, under the assumption that the discussed dynamical system is conservative⁹, the resulting Koopman operator is unitary. This enables one to obtain the Koopman modes directly via the projection on the corresponding orthonormal eigenfunction such that

$$\mathbf{v}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \langle g_1, \varphi_k \rangle \\ \langle g_2, \varphi_k \rangle \\ \vdots \\ \langle g_p, \varphi_k \rangle \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.40)$$

where $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ denotes the standard inner product defined within the spanned Hilbert space¹⁰.

Coming back to the general case, one may denote the evolution of the observables \mathbf{g} as

$$\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}_k) = \mathcal{K}_t^k \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \mathcal{K}_t^k \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \varphi_k(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{v}_k \quad (2.41)$$

$$= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \mathcal{K}_t^k \varphi_k(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{v}_k \quad (2.42)$$

$$= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k^k \varphi_k(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{v}_k \quad (2.43)$$

This infinite-dimensional set of of triples $\{(\lambda_k, \varphi_k, \mathbf{v}_k)\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$ is often referred to as the *Koopman mode decomposition* and provides a tight connection to the DMD, which will be elaborated later on.

Note that, as already demonstrated above, one may exploit such representation particularly regarding the evolution of the system i.e.

$$\mathcal{K}_t \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathcal{K}_t \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \varphi_k(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{v}_k = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \mathcal{K}_t \varphi_k(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{v}_k = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k \varphi_k(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{v}_k \quad (2.44)$$

Thus, considering the formulation of \mathbf{g} in equation 2.39, it becomes clear, that advancing the observable is equivalent to a simple multiplication with the Koopman eigenvalue.

⁹meaning that there is no dissipating energy, e.g. due to friction. Consequently, no attractors can appear within the phase space. The contrary constitutes a dissipative system

¹⁰typically, the measure is given by the Lebesgue square integral, thus $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty}$

2.3.1 Finite approximation and invariant subspaces

However, having discussed the benefits of Koopman analysis, we now have to come back to the main disadvantage already stated at the very beginning of this section, which is the infinite-dimensionality of the regarded space.

Thus, to ensure the practical application of the results, one endeavours a good approximation of such.

Precisely, one aims to derive a *Koopman-invariant finite* set of measurement functions $\{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_p\}$ which remains *invariant* under the application of the Koopman operator, such that for any linear combination

$$\mathbf{g} = \alpha_1 g_1 + \alpha_2 g_2 + \dots + \alpha_p g_p$$

the image of the application of the Koopman operator still remains in its subspace hence resulting into yet another linear combination of the defined basis vectors, i.e.

$$\mathcal{K}\mathbf{g} = \beta_1 g_1 + \beta_2 g_2 + \dots + \beta_p g_p$$

By means of that, one may generate a matrix-wise definition $\tilde{\mathbf{K}}$ of such approximation by setting the matrix components as $g_k(\mathbf{x})$. Note, that given the eigenfunctions, one may obtain such invariance by construction. Unfortunately, a good method for the identification of such remains an open-challenge until this point. Instead, it is currently more likely to derive an *almost-invariant* subspace $\{g_k\}_{k=1}^p$ such that $g_k \approx \sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_k \varphi_k$

In general, as one may already assume, the success of the Koopman operator is strongly correlated to the choice of measurement functions. Unfortunately, finding these is a highly nontrivial endeavour under the assumption of a purely-data driven method. Approaches of such exist, e.g. the *Sparse identification of nonlinear dynamics* (SINDys) (cf. [3]), though they won't be further elaborated within this work. Instead, one may remark that it is currently more common to pursue at least partial insights into the system, and/or combine such with more or less random guesses of a suitable basis.

Having scrutinized the core theory behind Koopman, let us observe its effectiveness by means of a concrete example.

2.3.2 Example - nonlinear dynamical system

By considering the nonlinear dynamical system

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= \mu x_1 \\ \dot{x}_2 &= \lambda(x_2 - x_1^2) \end{aligned} \tag{2.45}$$

we realize, that for $\lambda < \mu < 0$ the dynamics converge against an attracting manifold given as $x_2 = x_1^2$.

We follow the approach of Koopman by defining measurement functions g_i as

$$\begin{bmatrix} g_1 \\ g_2 \\ g_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_1^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.46)$$

such that one obtains a transformed *linear* dynamical system as

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} g_1 \\ g_2 \\ g_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda & -\lambda \\ 0 & 0 & 2\mu \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} g_1 \\ g_2 \\ g_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.47)$$

The first two equations trivially include the original system, whereas the last may be easily verified as

$$\frac{d}{dt} g_3 = \frac{d}{dt} x_1^2 = 2x_1 \dot{x}_1 \stackrel{\text{2nd DE}}{=} 2\mu x_1^2 = 2\mu g_3$$

Convinced of the validity of results, its behaviour will be presumably best outlined via the following graphic:

Figure 2.7: Visualization of the Koopman expansion on the given example. The attracting manifold $g_2 = x_2 = x_1^2$, a simple parabola in the original space is expanded by the third component and encoded in red. The blue area denotes the set of initial conditions that obeys the restriction of $g_3 = x_1^2$. Note, that within the 3-dimensional Koopman space the expanded trajectories (encoded in black) converge as expected towards the fixed point. [4].

Even further, if one projects the state of observables y_i back to the original system, hereby given as the x_1x_2 -/ y_1y_2 - plane, one may be convinced that the exact same behaviour of the *nonlinear* state is captured within the *linear* system which demonstrates the effectiveness of Koopman.

This visualization highlights the aspect that the whole concept of Koopman relies on nothing else than a (nonlinear) *coordinate transform*, hence just a different representation of the *exact same system*, which happened to be more favorable to critical insight, i.e. behaves linearly.

However, of course, one must remark that this is an example explicitly constructed for demonstrative reasons. Examples, where the observable functions might not be derived so easily, resulting in an actual infinite-dimensional function space, is e.g. given by the logistic map and further analyzed by Brunton [3].

In general, there remains a lot to say about the Koopman operator, including some connections to ergodic theory, the Discrete Fourier Transform and the Perron-Frobenius operator, however, we will leave it here and instead observe its tight relation to the actual algorithm of interest within this thesis - the *Dynamic mode decomposition* [3, 14, 13, 15, 20].

3 Dynamic Mode Decomposition

At this point, it may have become evident, that the Koopman operator provides plenty of useful properties and actually does perform effectively - *under the condition* that one chooses the set of observables g_i suitably.

We have already discussed, that this is unfortunately a highly non-trivial matter, which with high fidelity relies on at least partial insight into the system. Such constraint, however, is exactly what we wanted to avoid in the first place and contradicts our demand for a *data-driven* technique.

That is when the *Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD)* falls into place. Up-front connecting the two methods, let us introduce the latter.

In contrast to Koopman’s approach in 1931, the algorithm may be classified as a rather new technique, as it was developed lately in 2009/2010 by Peter J. Schmid [21, 22]. His main ambition was the construction of a purely *data-driven* method, independent of the concrete knowledge of a system matrix \mathbf{A} , which was nonetheless capable of revealing dominant spatio-temporal patterns. As a result to this specificity, it may be equally applied to simulations (implying dependency), as well as completely raw data, collected e.g. as measurements within experimental setups.

As consistent throughout this thesis, we are once again investigating a dynamical system which may be sampled at a constant time rate t . As the first step of this algorithm, one organizes the resulting time series into two overlapping matrices via the method of snapshots such that the first is given as

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} | & | & & | \\ \mathbf{x}_0 & \mathbf{x}_1 & \cdots & \mathbf{x}_{n-1} \\ | & | & & | \end{bmatrix} \tag{3.1}$$

and the second analogously, though shifted one step t in time, as

$$\mathbf{X}' = \begin{bmatrix} | & | & & | \\ \mathbf{x}_1 & \mathbf{x}_2 & \cdots & \mathbf{x}_n \\ | & | & & | \end{bmatrix} \tag{3.2}$$

To put it in a nutshell, if $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n}$ then

- m = the number of components which constitute one time snapshot
- n = the number of snapshots taken over the considered time interval

For instance, thinking of one snapshot as a sole image, of e.g. a fluid flow, m could be imagined as the number of given pixels. To comply with our definition, these are subsequently flattened into a single tall one-dimensional vector, constituting a separate column in the resulting matrix \mathbf{X} .

One may herewith remark, that, of course, one would *never* construct both $m \times n$ matrices explicitly, but rather seek a more reasonable approach. For instance, one could store the first/ last snapshot within a separate vector, or simply slice one large $m \times (n + 1)$ matrix appropriately. For theoretical clarity, we will however retain the stated notation and continue with the second step of the DMD.

The objection of such is, as motivated by the advantageous properties stated within the last chapter, the derivation of an approximately *linear* relation between the two snapshot matrices such that

$$\mathbf{X}' \cong \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X}, \quad \mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times m} \quad (3.3)$$

One may remark that the effect of such operator \mathbf{A} is congruent to a flow map \mathbf{F}_t (cf. 2.4), as it advances all of the snapshots within \mathbf{X} one step forward in time. This justifies the time-shifted arrangement, as it yields the most promising potential to gain meaningful insight into supposed underlying dominant (spatio-)temporal patterns.

However, as previously discussed, it is evident, that, apart from the rarest occasion of an actually existing exact linear relation, one may *approximate* it in an optimized least-squares sense. Precisely, one aims to minimize the residual matrix

$$\|\mathbf{X}' - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X}\|_F \quad (3.4)$$

measured within the Frobenius norm defined as

$$\|\mathbf{X}\|_F = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^m \mathbf{X}_{jk}^2} \quad (3.5)$$

A solution is given via the Moore-Penrose pseudoinverse \mathbf{X}^\dagger of \mathbf{X}^1 hence obtaining

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X}^\dagger \quad (3.6)$$

We will discuss the actual computation of \mathbf{X}^\dagger as well as the practical implementations of the DMD at a further point within this chapter.

¹This may be further clarified, if one remarks that for an exactly solvable system $\mathbf{X}' = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X} \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X}^{-1}$

However, we may herewith dissolve the connection towards the theory of Koopmanism discussed in the last chapter. Precisely, one may state, that the computed matrix \mathbf{A} (as well as the assigned eigenvectors) actually does constitute an approximation of the Koopman operator \mathcal{K} alongside its modes [3, 14]. This becomes particularly evident under the consideration of the core purpose of both techniques - The derivation of a *model/operator* which establishes an approximately linear system behaviour (within a likely nonlinear context). It is therefore straight-forward to derive its spectral decomposition which allows us to complete the theory for the algorithm as a whole.

Theorem 5 (Dynamic Mode Decomposition). *Regarding a dynamical system and two sets of data \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}' as defined in 3.1, 3.2 such that $\mathbf{x}'_k = \mathbf{F}_t(\mathbf{x}_k)$ where \mathbf{F}_t is the flow map as in 2, the Dynamic Mode Decomposition aims to compute the leading eigendecomposition of \mathbf{A} such that*

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{u}_i = \lambda_i\mathbf{u}_i \quad (3.7)$$

\mathbf{A} hereby denotes the best-fit linear operator corresponding to the linear regression problem $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X}^\dagger$.

The eigenvectors \mathbf{u}_i belonging to a specific eigenvalue λ_i are called dynamic, or DMD modes.

To visualize some results, we will present a toy example provided by the python DMD library PyDMD². The code can be found using [18].

First of all, we construct a snapshot matrix \mathbf{X} as the sum of

$$\begin{aligned} f_1 &= \text{sech}(x + 3)\exp(i2.3t) \\ f_2 &= 2\text{sech}(x)\tanh(x)\exp(i2.8t) \end{aligned}$$

sampled in 256 time-equidistant points at 128 parameters x , hence $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{C}^{256 \times 128}$. Within the graphics, we however transposed the matrices to improve the visualization structure.

Figure 3.1: Generated dynamical system out of the sum of f_1 and f_2 . (From left to right: $f_1, f_2, f_1 + f_2$) [18].

Having computed the DMD, the modes and dynamics could be derived and plotted as in 3.2.

²GitHub: <https://mathlab.github.io/PyDMD/>

Figure 3.2: Extracted modes (left) and dynamics (right) of the system used to reconstruct the original system [18].

As discussed, such may be exploited to reconstruct the dynamics as depicted in figure 3.3. It is evident, that the DMD performs notably well for this toy

Figure 3.3: Reconstructed dynamical system via DMD modes [18].

example. However, one may herewith emphasize that it was only included to further build intuition on the actual results of the algorithm[18]. A slightly more complex example including noise/denoising with respect to the DMD, as well as an animation of the results is given by [19]. One may be encouraged to observe them on one's own.

Hence, having grasped the main idea of the DMD, one may approach its computation. Two coarse-grained techniques are associated with such. On the one hand, the *Arnoldi iteration* and on the other, the *Singular Value Decomposition*. Both will be presented separately and compared to each other in the following.

3.1 Version 1 - Arnoldi based approach

Within the original creation of the Dynamic Mode Decomposition [22], Peter J. Schmid mainly relied on the technique of *Arnoldi iteration*. For that reason,

upfront associating it further with the DMD, we will quickly attain to grasp its core concepts.

3.1.1 Arnoldi iteration

Theorem 6 (Arnoldi iteration). *The Arnoldi iteration constitutes an iterative algorithm which transforms a given matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times m}$ to Hessenberg form \mathbf{H} ³ such that*

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{H}\mathbf{Q}^* \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{A}\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{H} \quad (3.8)$$

encodes an orthogonal similarity reduction.

If \mathbf{A} is self-adjoint, the Hessenberg matrix will have tridiagonal form and the Arnoldi iteration is referred to as the Lanczos iteration.

Note that this is exactly the type of transformation we require as the DMD still constitutes an *eigenproblem*, which relies on the reassurance of the unaltered magnitude of eigenvalues. In general, the reason to strive for a transformation to Hessenberg form is the resulting reduction of computational costs. The additional effort of this preprocessing step is typically counterbalanced by the improved performance of the subsequent spectral decomposition. This argument is specifically valid for operations on large matrices.

At this juncture, one may justifiably argue that a Hessenberg reduction may be equally computed via a (more stable) sequence of Householder reflections. However, there are some benefits associated with the Arnoldi technique, which will be outlined in the following.

First, in contrast to the Householder transformation, it particularly capitalizes on large and sparse matrices, leaving the specificity of sparseness untouched. As this type tends to be quite common within the practical application of dynamical systems, this property may yield considerable relevance.

Second, the Arnoldi iteration consists out of *column-wise* reductions. As a result, one may not transform the matrix to the whole extent, enabling the usage of *partial* results .

With this in mind, one may regard only the first n columns \mathbf{q}_i of \mathbf{Q} as

$$\mathbf{Q}_n = \left[\begin{array}{c|c|c|c} | & | & & | \\ \mathbf{q}_1 & \mathbf{q}_2 & \dots & \mathbf{q}_n \\ | & | & & | \end{array} \right] \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n} \quad (3.9)$$

³A quadratic matrix, which is (upper) triangular apart from the subdiagonal. If not indicating otherwise, Hessenberg is equivalent to *upper* Hessenberg form, though the contrary (lower Hessenberg) is also existent. In such case, the restriction applies analogously to the superdiagonal instead of the subdiagonal.

and the upper left fraction of \mathbf{H} as

$$\mathbf{H}_n = \begin{bmatrix} h_{11} & & \dots & h_{1n} \\ h_{21} & h_{22} & & \\ & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ & & h_{n,n-1} & h_{nn} \\ & & & h_{n+1,n} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{(n+1) \times n} \quad (3.10)$$

such that one obtains the partial reduction as

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{Q}_n = \mathbf{Q}_{n+1}\mathbf{H}_n \quad (3.11)$$

One may easily verify that the matrix-vector multiplication of the last column may be equivalently denoted as

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{q}_n = h_{1n}\mathbf{q}_1 + \dots + h_{nn}\mathbf{q}_n + h_{n+1,n}\mathbf{q}_{n+1} = \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} h_{k,n}\mathbf{q}_k \quad (3.12)$$

which reveals the recurrence relation alongside which the so called *Arnoldi vectors* \mathbf{q}_i have been built.

Justified by the column-wise nature of the algorithm, one may consequently generalize the formula to all columns such that

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{q}_k = \sum_{i=1}^{k+1} h_{i,k}\mathbf{q}_i, \quad 1 \leq k \leq n \quad (3.13)$$

where one may extract the last summand to obtain

$$h_{k+1,k}\mathbf{q}_{k+1} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{q}_k - \sum_{i=1}^k h_{i,k}\mathbf{q}_i := \mathbf{r}_k \quad (3.14)$$

or equivalently (under the condition that $\mathbf{r}_k \neq \mathbf{0}$)

$$\mathbf{q}_{k+1} = \frac{\mathbf{r}_k}{h_{k+1,k}} = \frac{\mathbf{r}_k}{\|\mathbf{r}_k\|} \quad (3.15)$$

where $h_{ik} = \mathbf{q}_i^* \mathbf{A}\mathbf{q}_k$ for $i = 1 : k$. The case of $\mathbf{r}_k = \mathbf{0}$ is excluded, as it indicates that the new basis vector which is projected on its predecessors was already within their spanned space, hence is linearly dependent on them. Consequentially, the dimension of the column space is reached and can't be surpassed. By means of that, it would destroy the *unreduced* nature of the Hessenberg matrix.

In sum, one may derive the algorithm as in the following [11, 25].

Algorithm 1: Arnoldi iteration

```

1 b = randomly generated or given initial vector
2 q1 = b/||b|| // Normalization
3 k = 1
4 r0 = q1
5 while k ≤ n do
6   rk = Aqk
7   for i = 1 to k // Orthogonalization
8     do
9     | hi,k = qi*rk
10    | rk = rk − hi,kqi
11    | hk+1,k = ||rk||
12    | if hk+1,k = 0 then
13    | | stop iterating and return partial result
14    | qk+1 = rk/hk+1,k // Normalization
15
16    | k = k + 1

```

This algorithm isn't reminiscent to the Gram-Schmidt process without reason. Precisely, the recurrence relation of such is defined as

$$\mathbf{q}_k = (\mathbf{a}_k - \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} r_{ik} \mathbf{q}_i) / r_{kk} \quad (3.16)$$

where $r_{ik} = \mathbf{q}_i^T \mathbf{a}_k$, $i = 1 : k - 1$, which may be easily compared to equations 3.14, 3.15 [11]. It is therefore evident that it constitutes a variation of it as the sole difference constitutes line 6, encoding the initial configuration of the next basis vector of \mathbf{Q}_k . It is chosen in such way, that it encaptures the proceeding of the system in a linear manner, hence

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_k \quad (3.17)$$

This assumption is reflected within the recurrence relation, which enables another interpretation of the Arnoldi iteration, i.e. the successive creation of orthonormal bases for the underlying *Krylov subspaces* $K_n(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{q}_1)$.

Definition 3 (Krylov subspace). *Given the equation $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b}$, with $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$, $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{C}^n$, the n^{th} -order Krylov subspace is generated by the first n powers of \mathbf{A} multiplied to the right-hand side \mathbf{b} , i.e.*

$$K_n(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{b}) = \text{span}\{\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{A}\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{A}^2\mathbf{b}, \dots, \mathbf{A}^{n-1}\mathbf{b}\} \subseteq \mathbb{C}^n \quad (3.18)$$

The set of basis vectors may be organized within a matrix, in which case it is referred to as the corresponding Krylov matrix

$$\mathbf{K}_n = \begin{bmatrix} | & | & & | \\ \mathbf{b} & \mathbf{A}\mathbf{b} & \dots & \mathbf{A}^{n-1}\mathbf{b} \\ | & | & & | \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.19)$$

To put it differently, one orthogonally projects \mathbf{A} onto the generated Krylov subspaces K_n . As a result, one may rewrite equation 3.8 as

$$\mathbf{H}_n = \mathbf{Q}_n^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{Q}_n$$

Projections of such kind are e.g. exploited within the *Rayleigh-Ritz procedure*, used to extract eigenvalues iteratively [25]. By the same manner, one may notice that the diagonal entries of \mathbf{H}_n are given as the Rayleigh quotients⁴ This highlights the purpose of this algorithm, which is, inter alia, the derivation of an approximative eigenproblem solution. Precisely, one may state that the eigenvalues of \mathbf{H} constitute approximations of those of the original matrix. For that reason, they are referred to as the *Arnoldi eigenvalue estimates* or *Ritz values* of \mathbf{A} [11, 25].

3.1.2 DMD - Original Arnoldi approach

Regarding the Arnoldi iteration out of a DMD perspective, one may object, that the algorithm induces dependency on the system matrix \mathbf{A} . However, this doesn't reflect the entire truth. In fact, it just relies on the knowledge of the *effect* of the operator. In other words, the only feature that must be provided is the application of \mathbf{A} to a vector \mathbf{x} , satisfying $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}$ ⁵. Consequently, one could exploit the Arnoldi iteration to the full extent without any further information about the system matrix. This offers some potential, which was capitalized by Schmid.

Incidentally, one may remark, that the application of a matrix to a vector, hence the *evolution* of a system (state) perfectly falls in line with the theory of dynamical systems⁶. As we constructed the matrix \mathbf{X} out of a sequence

⁴:= $r(x) = \frac{x^* \mathbf{A} x}{x^* x} = h_{nn}$ for $x \in \mathbb{C}^n$. Notice that if x is an eigenvector, $r(x)$ denotes the corresponding eigenvalue.

⁵Note that this could be for example encoded within a private subroutine, in a black box manner, hence only accessible via its interface

⁶More precisely, we might interpret the operator \mathbf{A} as a form of flow map

of snapshots, we may assume that they are or at least can be approximately connected in a linear manner, such that equation 3.17 may be applied. Consequently, as already stated, we may grasp them as a Krylov sequence

$$\mathbf{X}_0^{N-1} = \{\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{A}^2\mathbf{x}_0, \dots, \mathbf{A}^{N-1}\mathbf{x}_0\} \cong \mathbf{X} \quad (3.20)$$

⁷ facilitating the computation of the spectral properties. Furthermore, due to our assumption of dominant low-rank structures within our system, it follows that as of a specific number (i.e. r) of basis vectors, its rank r is reached. To put it the other way around, due to the high-dimensional construction (in spite of a presumable low intrinsic rank), one may assume linear dependence as of a critical threshold, such that a snapshot may be expressed as

$$\mathbf{x}_N = a_0\mathbf{x}_0 + a_1\mathbf{x}_1 + \dots + a_{N-1}\mathbf{x}_{N-1} + \mathbf{r} \quad (3.21)$$

hence a linear combination of the extracted r (in this case for notational reasons denoted as N) basis vectors with \mathbf{r} encapsuring the residual vector. Equivalently, we may choose a representation in matrix form as

$$\mathbf{x}_N = \mathbf{X}_0^{N-2}\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{r} \quad (3.22)$$

where $\mathbf{X}_0^{N-2} = \{\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{N-2}\}$ and $\mathbf{a}^T = \{a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{N-2}\}$ captures the contributions of each basis vector. By exploiting this relation one may formulate the application of \mathbf{A} as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A}\{\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{N-2}\} &= \mathbf{X}_1^{N-1} = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{N-1}\} \\ &= \{\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{X}_0^{N-2}\mathbf{a}\} + \mathbf{r}\mathbf{e}_{N-1}^T \\ &= \mathbf{X}_0^{N-2}\mathbf{C} + \mathbf{r}\mathbf{e}_{N-1}^T \end{aligned} \quad (3.23)$$

where \mathbf{e}_{N-1} equals the $(N-1)^{th}$ unit vector [22]. Furthermore, one may realize that

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & & & a_0 \\ 1 & 0 & & a_1 \\ & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ & & 1 & 0 & a_{N-3} \\ & & & 1 & a_{N-2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.24)$$

is a companion matrix, emphasizing the aspect, that the successive snapshot matrix \mathbf{X}^t is just shifted one step t in time. One may hence state, that the eigenvalues of \mathbf{C} approximate some of the eigenvalues of \mathbf{H} , as within the

⁷Explanation of the notation \mathbf{X}_a^b for the Krylov sequence: The sub- and superscript denote the first and last index of an (equidistantly) sampled snapshot range/ the order of the represented Krylov subspace. Thus, in this case, one would regard a sequence of $\mathcal{K} = \{\mathbf{x}_a, \mathbf{x}_{a+1}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_b\}$

original Arnoldi approach. However, to avoid dependencies on the system matrix, one has to seek a varying approach regarding the derivation of the matrix \mathbf{C} , respectively, its last column, as the remaining information is trivially induced. In this sense, under the awareness of the *meaning* of the *evolution* \mathbf{A} and the Krylov sequence (though we won't construct it explicitly), we aim to obtain its components a_i in a least-squares sense, such that

$$\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{R}^{-1}\mathbf{Q}^*\mathbf{x}_N \quad (3.25)$$

given that $\mathbf{X}_0^{N-2} = \mathbf{QR}$ has full rank. Hence, we aim to obtain a solution via the minimization of the residual defined in 3.22.

In sum, as within the pure Arnoldi iteration, we have deduced an approximation of the spectral properties and introduced a *purely data-driven* method via the omittance of the dependence on the system matrix. However, though this Arnoldi-like DMD is commonly used for proofs regarding convergence analysis and beneficial with respect to general understanding, as it is closely related to the Krylov subspaces, it does not constitute the prevalent technique for the computation of the Dynamic Mode Decomposition.

The reason for its inferiority is its ill-conditioned nature. Note, that in contrast to its model, this algorithm omits the successive orthogonalization of each basis vector. This introduces particular severe consequences in case of a large contamination with noise, which is, as we discussed early on in this thesis, unfortunately pretty common within practical applications.

Hence, we will introduce a more commonly accepted and robust variant of the Dynamic Mode Decomposition within the next chapter, which demonstrates improved stability attributes [21, 22, 23].

3.2 Version 2 - SVD based approach

Precisely, one way to defy the challenge of noise contamination in a more sophisticated manner may be constructed via the *Singular Value Decomposition*, which will be quickly outlined below.

Theorem 7 (Singular value decomposition). *Given an arbitrary matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n}$, the singular value decomposition is guaranteed to exist and may be described as the factorization of*

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^* \quad (3.26)$$

where

$$\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times m}, \mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$$

are unitary matrices and

$$\mathbf{\Sigma} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n}, \quad \mathbf{\Sigma} = \text{diag}(\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_p), \quad p = \min(m, n)$$

is a diagonal matrix with

$$\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \sigma_p \geq 0.$$

The first p columns of U and V are hereby called left and right singular vectors, whereas $\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_p$ denote the singular values [11].

From now on, we assume $m \geq n$ without loss of generality, as analogous statements may be easily obtained by adapting the corresponding dimensions. This also reflects the vast majority of use cases within practical applications.

One particular benefit of this decomposition relies in its relation towards the spaces spanned by a specific system [23, 24]. Concretely, we may state that

Corollary 7.1. *If \mathbf{A} has r positive singular values, therefore*

$$\sigma_1 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_r > \sigma_{r+1} = \dots = \sigma_p = 0$$

then

$$\text{rank}(\mathbf{A}) = r$$

and

$$\text{null}(\mathbf{A}) = \text{span}\{\mathbf{v}_{r+1}, \dots, \mathbf{v}_n\}$$

$$\text{ran}(\mathbf{A}) = \text{span}\{\mathbf{u}_1, \dots, \mathbf{u}_r\}$$

$$\text{null}(\mathbf{A}^*) = \text{span}\{\mathbf{u}_{r+1}, \dots, \mathbf{u}_m\}$$

$$\text{ran}(\mathbf{A}^*) = \text{span}\{\mathbf{v}_1, \dots, \mathbf{v}_r\}$$

In our setup, reminded that the data matrices \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{X}' comprise a time series of snapshots, the column space encaptures informations about the proceeding of the system in *time*, whereas the row space contains core features of the underlying *spatial* structures. Due to the hierarchical arrangement of the singular values, the order of the corresponding basis vectors of the spaces spanned by \mathbf{U}, \mathbf{V} follows correspondingly. This may already indicate the potential associated with the main ambition of the *Dynamic Mode Decomposition*, i.e. the revelation of *dominant, presuambly low-rank* spatio-temporal patterns of the system.

Moreover, one may save memory under the awareness of potential rank-deficiency of \mathbf{A} by operating on a reduced variant of this decomposition, known as the *Truncated SVD*.

Theorem 8 (Truncated SVD). *If $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{U}\Sigma\mathbf{V}^* \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n}$ is the SVD of a rank- r matrix \mathbf{A} and*

$$\hat{\mathbf{U}} = \{\mathbf{u}_1, \dots, \mathbf{u}_t\}, \quad \hat{\Sigma} = \text{diag}(\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_t), \quad \hat{\mathbf{V}} = \{\mathbf{v}_1, \dots, \mathbf{v}_t\}$$

such that $\hat{\mathbf{U}} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times t}$, $\hat{\mathbf{\Sigma}} \in \mathbb{C}^{t \times t}$, $\hat{\mathbf{V}} \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times t}$ then

$$\mathbf{A} \cong \hat{\mathbf{U}} \hat{\mathbf{\Sigma}} \hat{\mathbf{V}}^* = \sum_{i=1}^t \sigma_i \mathbf{u}_i \mathbf{v}_i^*$$

defines the *Truncated SVD* of \mathbf{A} . If $t = r$, one may also refer to it as the *Thin SVD* which provides an exact representation of \mathbf{A} .

With that in mind and still aware of the increased stability objective, one may deduce the first step of the DMD, which is the computation of the (eventually truncated) singular value decomposition of \mathbf{X} as

$$\mathbf{X} = \hat{\mathbf{U}} \hat{\mathbf{\Sigma}} \hat{\mathbf{V}}^* \quad (3.27)$$

Inter alia depending on the (descent rate of the) spectrum of singular values one may decide to deviate from the exact representation and operate on a further reduced matrix where $t < r$. It was proven in a theorem originally established by Schmidt, that the resulting partial sum actually is the optimal low-rank approximation of \mathbf{A} in the Frobenius and ℓ_2 -norm. Rediscovered later by Eckhart and Young, it is known as the *Eckhart-Young Theorem*.

Theorem 9 (Eckhart-Young Theorem). *Suppose $t < r = \text{rank}(\mathbf{A})$ and*

$$\mathbf{A}_t = \sum_{i=1}^t \sigma_i \mathbf{u}_i \mathbf{v}_i^* = \mathbf{U}_t \mathbf{\Sigma}_t \mathbf{V}_t^*$$

then

$$\min_{\text{rank}(\mathbf{A}_t)=t} \|\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{A}_t\|_2 = \sigma_{t+1}$$

and even more

$$\mathbf{A}_t = \arg \min_{\text{rg}(\mathbf{B})=t} \|\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}\|_2$$

Apart from being more favorable for memory and computation, this might inhabit the chance to denoise the data and is indeed accepted as a regularization technique [8]. On the other hand, truncation also encaptures the risk of loosing relevant information. Particularly, in some dynamical systems, even small contributions might lead to disruptive, hence crucial behaviour, which emphasizes its importance e.g. in the context of control whilst simultaneously impeding energy-based heuristics. To put it in a nutshell - The choice of such threshold is highly non-trivial and amply discussed among practitioners [3, 6, 14]. One may remark, that the choice of t also determines the amount of dynamic modes one will obtain. This will become evident at a later point of this analysis.

With this in mind, we will come back to the general proceeding of the *Dynamic Mode Decomposition* alongside its main objective, i.e. the derivation of

the spectral decomposition of a best-fit linear operator \mathbf{A} , which one aims to establish subsequently.

Thus, as priori discussed in equation 3.6 it may be established in an optimal least-squares sense via the pseudoinverse as

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{X}' \underbrace{\hat{\mathbf{V}} \hat{\Sigma}^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{U}}^*}_{\mathbf{x}^\dagger} \quad (3.28)$$

with $\hat{\Sigma}^{-1} = \text{diag}(1/\sigma_1, 1/\sigma_2, \dots, 1/\sigma_r, 0, \dots, 0)$.

Nonetheless, one may realize that this would result into $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times m}$. As we assume, that $m \gg n$, hence, the amount of state parameters to be presumably significantly larger than the number of snapshots (e.g. $10^6 - 10^9$ compared to a few thousands), \mathbf{A} could grow to prohibitive amounts. One may be reminded though, that the true objective is not the construction of such matrix, but first and foremost its actual purpose, i.e. the *application* as an operator. Considering the interpretation of column and row spaces, such is equivalent to the evolution of the system in time (which may be realized by means of its spectral decomposition as the operator is constructed to behave approximatively linear).

Hence, *instead of ever computing \mathbf{A} explicitly*, it is reasonable to project the data onto a low-dimensional space. More precisely, project it in such manner, that the maximum of attainable information is preserved. Once again, one may exploit the properties of the singular value decomposition within this context, as it obeys such requirements. Precisely, we project \mathbf{A} onto the lower-dimensional column space, as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \hat{\mathbf{U}}^* \mathbf{A} \hat{\mathbf{U}} = \hat{\mathbf{U}}^* \mathbf{X}' \hat{\mathbf{V}} \hat{\Sigma}^{-1} \quad (3.29)$$

And can hence advance our state in the altered space of coherent spatial structures as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k \quad (3.30)$$

which is significantly less expensive than operating on the full space. Nevertheless, it is always possible to remap the reduced model to the original via

$$\mathbf{x} = \hat{\mathbf{U}} \tilde{\mathbf{x}} \quad (3.31)$$

Regarding this equation, one may notice, that we projected \mathbf{A} onto the column space, in our case inhabiting the *spatial* coherent structures. Thus, if one would like to correlate the decomposition to others of the field, one may consider the Principle Component Analysis (PCA), which is in the context of fluid dynamics more commonly known as Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD).⁸ Through this lens, the columns of \mathbf{U} would correspond to the POD

⁸In fact, it appears in various contexts under various names, i.e., among others, the Karhunen-Loève (KL) decomposition, empirical orthogonal functions (EOF), ...

modes. However, in contrast to both techniques, one may realize that the DMD omits second-order statistics, hence typically does *not* include any kind of averaging process with respect to spatial or temporal behaviour. This leads to a higher potential of unbiased insight into the system dynamics.

Additionally, one may precisely remark that the projection into the lower-dimensional space does *not* alter the eigenvalues of the matrix, thus, it is sufficient to work *directly* on $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$, especially with respect to its eigendecomposition

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{\Lambda} \quad (3.32)$$

However, despite the successful computation of the *DMD eigenvalues*, one still lacks the corresponding high-dimensional *DMD modes* Φ .

Precisely, the remapping of such onto the *original* higher-dimensional space may be achieved via

$$\Phi = \mathbf{X}'\hat{\mathbf{V}}\hat{\mathbf{\Sigma}}^{-1}\mathbf{W} \quad (3.33)$$

which might not seem straightforward at first. Nevertheless, it actually does guarantee the exact reconstruction of the eigenvectors, as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A}\Phi &= (\mathbf{X}'\hat{\mathbf{V}}\hat{\mathbf{\Sigma}}^{-1}\hat{\mathbf{U}}^*)\underbrace{(\mathbf{X}'\hat{\mathbf{V}}\hat{\mathbf{\Sigma}}^{-1}\mathbf{W})}_{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}} \\ &= \mathbf{X}'\hat{\mathbf{V}}\hat{\mathbf{\Sigma}}^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{W} \\ &\stackrel{3.32}{=} \underbrace{\mathbf{X}'\hat{\mathbf{V}}\hat{\mathbf{\Sigma}}^{-1}\mathbf{W}}_{\Phi}\mathbf{\Lambda} \\ &= \Phi\mathbf{\Lambda} \end{aligned}$$

In the original paper of Schmid, the reconstruction of the DMD modes was achieved following equation 3.31 as

$$\Phi = \hat{\mathbf{U}}\mathbf{W} \quad (3.34)$$

which are consequently referred to as *projected DMD modes*. One may convince oneself that they do *not* necessarily exhibit an exact representation as 3.33, as \mathbf{A} was constructed as $\mathbf{X}\mathbf{X}^\dagger$. Hence, the eigenvectors of \mathbf{A} are expected to be spanned within the column space of the advanced \mathbf{X}' instead of the original state matrix \mathbf{X} . The latter however, is indicated in the projected DMD mode variant, as the basis $\hat{\mathbf{U}}$ belongs to the SVD computed on \mathbf{X} . Nevertheless, one may fairly admit that in many cases, with increased certainty in the case of a very fine-granular discretization, the column spaces of \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{X}' will be nearly identical as a result of their high correlation.

However, to provide the most accurate solution one might attain, we will choose the exact variant and may finally state the full algorithm as

Algorithm 2: Dynamic Mode Decomposition (via SVD)

- 1 $\mathbf{X} = \hat{\mathbf{U}}\hat{\Sigma}\hat{\mathbf{V}}^*$
 - 2 $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \hat{\mathbf{U}}^*\mathbf{X}'\hat{\mathbf{V}}\hat{\Sigma}^{-1}$
 - 3 $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}\Lambda$
 - 4 $\Phi = \mathbf{X}'\hat{\mathbf{V}}\hat{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{W}$
-

Let us quickly summarize what we have done so far. First, we considered (theoretically) an operator \mathbf{A} which realized a quasi-linear mapping in an optimal least-squares sense. Afterwards, to avoid the computation of a potentially large matrix such as \mathbf{A} , we reduced the dimensionality of the operator via an orthogonal projection onto the column space of \mathbf{X} . Due to aforementioned relation, we could then deduce the unaltered magnitude of the eigenvalues, which justified lastly the more efficient computation of the spectral decomposition within the reduced space. However, to ensure meaningful insight on our original system of interest, we reprojected the eigenvectors back to the high-dimensional space.

Hence, the only thing left to consider is the main reason why we took the spectral properties into account in the first place, i.e. the prediction of the *evolution* of a dynamical system. For that reason, one may quickly recall the exact solution stated in equation 2.32 of subsection 2.2.2 as

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{V}e^{\Lambda t}\mathbf{V}^{-1}\mathbf{x}_0$$

Unfortunately, as the sole use case of the Dynamic Mode Decomposition is a quasi-linear mapping for presumably *nonlinear* systems, we have to make a few adjustments. Precisely, we will obtain

$$\mathbf{x}(t) \approx \Phi e^{\Lambda t} \underbrace{\Phi^\dagger \mathbf{x}_0}_{:=\mathbf{b}} = \sum_{j=1}^t \phi_j e^{\lambda_j t} b_j \quad (3.35)$$

where Φ denotes the computed DMD modes corresponding to the eigenvalues λ_i captured in $\Lambda := \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_r)$ ⁹. b_k defines the amplitude associated with each mode. Note that the initial state \mathbf{x}_0 of the system is hereby represented by the first snapshot, or rather column, of \mathbf{X} [3, 14, 22].

Analogous results can be obtained in the discrete case considering equation 2.34 as

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{V}\Lambda^{k-1}\mathbf{V}^{-1}\mathbf{x}_0$$

mapping to

$$\mathbf{x}_k \approx \Phi \Lambda^{k-1} \underbrace{\Phi^\dagger \mathbf{x}_0}_{:=\mathbf{b}} = \sum_{j=1}^t \phi_j \lambda_j^{k-1} b_j \quad (3.36)$$

⁹In fluid dynamics, the eigenvalues are often mapped to a logarithmic scale, as $\omega_i = \log(\lambda_i)/\Delta t$ such that $\Lambda = \Omega := \text{diag}(\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_r)$. This is inter alia done to improve the separation between stable (modulus < 1) and unstable eigenvalues (modulus > 1), as after such transformation they exhibit negative, positive real part respectively [22]

One may remark, that the only non-derived component within this equation is the vector of coefficients b_i . And though the approach given by the pseudo-inverts is mathematically fully valid, one may remark that the resulting pseudoinverse is potentially - depending on the choice of truncation t - high-dimensional hence inducing expensive computations. That becomes even worse if one considers that one usually would like to advance the state not only one, but multiple times, accumulating the loss of performance even further. Consequently, one could consider an alternative computation of \mathbf{b} once again within the low-rank projected space such that

$$\mathbf{x}_0 = \Phi \mathbf{b}$$

is computed in the projected space substituting equations 3.31, 3.33 as

$$\begin{aligned} \Leftrightarrow \hat{\mathbf{U}}\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0 &= \mathbf{X}'\hat{\mathbf{V}}\hat{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{W} \\ \Leftrightarrow \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0 &= \hat{\mathbf{U}}^*\mathbf{X}'\hat{\mathbf{V}}\hat{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{W} \\ \Leftrightarrow \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0 &= \tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{W}\mathbf{b} \\ \Leftrightarrow \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0 &= \mathbf{W}\Lambda\mathbf{b} \\ \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{b} &= (\mathbf{W}\Lambda^{-1})\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0 \end{aligned} \tag{3.37}$$

This might be advantageous, as $\mathbf{W}, \Lambda \in \mathbb{C}^{t \times t}$, whereas $\Phi \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times t}$ [3].

Incidentally, one may notice that the DMD in general does *not* put any restriction upon the construction of the data matrix \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}' respectively. Hence, it would be completely valid to simply transpose the matrices/ rearrange them such that the snapshots would be aligned row-wise, instead of column-wise. Alternatively, one could adapt the algorithm by taking the properties of the singular value decomposition into account. Precisely, one may decide to project the data onto the row, instead of the column space and proceed analogously. This would lead to equivalent results.

Having scrutinized the theory of the algorithm, one may think about the challenges and strategies of a concrete implementation, which will be outlined by means of some already existing exemplary libraries within the next chapter.

4 Implementations

We have seen that Dynamic Mode Decomposition achieves dimensionality reduction by deriving modes and eigenvalues of a large best-fit linear operator \mathbf{A} *without* its explicit computation. This technique however, at least in the commonly implemented variant 2, relies on a Singular Value Decomposition of the original data, which in itself may be computationally prohibitive for larger datasets.

Available solutions to the SVD memory bottleneck typically use one of two approaches:

- memory-distributed calculations
- randomized linear algebra

We will discuss these two techniques by illustrating existing libraries that provide corresponding implemented components. Finally, at the end of this chapter we will consider the possibility of a hybrid solution for the DMD algorithm, in terms of a combination of the two perspectives.

4.1 Parallel (Distributed) - Modred

Modred is a model reduction library written in Python and developed at Princeton University. Apart from implementations of the Dynamic Mode Decompositions, it provides other reduction model techniques, such as the (Balanced) Proper Orthogonal Decomposition ((B)POD), Petrov-Galerkin Projection, or the Eigensystem Realization Algorithm (ERA). Many of them are parallelized for distributed architectures via MPI, respectively its Python interface `mpi4py`. Apart from that, it provides various optimization techniques. First, it offers the opportunity to tailor the software to the given problem size. It hereby distinguishes between two types of data

Small - The snapshot matrix $\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{X}')$ can be stored *completely* in the memory of a single node

Medium - \mathbf{X} (as well as the resulting matrix Φ) is too large to fit in the memory of a single node, but individual snapshots are sufficiently small to fit in memory

Everything not captured within these two distinctions may be referred to as **Large** and defines the situation in which vectors are too large to fit in a single node's memory at once. This third case is not covered by the library, whereas the remaining are implemented separately.

The first, developed for smaller use cases, is based on the assumption that the snapshot matrix $\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{X}')$ fits in memory and hence may be fully constructed following the semantics which have been discussed earlier in this thesis. Analogously, it operates on the previously introduced DMD-SVD algorithm 2, following the original computation over the corresponding matrix products. The second reformulates the original algorithm by binding it solely to the constraint of a *vector space*. The vector space (in the sense of modred) must provide an inner product, scalar multiplication, as well as a vector addition¹.

Furthermore, instead of computing the SVD directly, modred's distributed implementation relies on the connection to the underlying eigenproblem, i.e.

Corollary 9.1. *If $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{U}\Sigma\mathbf{V}^*$ is the SVD of \mathbf{A} and $\mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{v}_i, i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$, $p = \min(m, n)$ are the first p columns of \mathbf{U}, \mathbf{V} then*

$$\mathbf{A}^* \mathbf{A} \mathbf{v}_i = \sigma_i^2 \mathbf{v}_i$$

$$\mathbf{A} \mathbf{A}^* \mathbf{u}_i = \sigma_i^2 \mathbf{u}_i$$

as well as

$$\mathbf{A} \mathbf{v}_i = \sigma_i \mathbf{u}_i$$

Note that as $\mathbf{A}^* \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{A} \mathbf{A}^*$ are regular by construction, as each element is composed out of an inner product, which is by definition symmetric and positive definite, the resulting eigenvalues, respectively singular values, will be real and positive in every case. As a result, the eigenvalues $\lambda_p, p = \min(m, n)$ will be easily obtained as

$$\lambda_p = \sigma_p^2 \tag{4.1}$$

whilst the remaining $|m - n|$ eigenvalues equal 0 [11].

The reason for the recollection to the underlying problem is that it is advantageous to the parallelization strategy of the library, which inter alia relies on the parallelization of inner products. As previously discussed, they compose the elements of the correlation matrix $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{A}^* \mathbf{A}$.

¹In Python terms: a *vector* is an object, if it provides the following methods: `__add__`/`__+`, `__mul__`/`__*`, `inner_product(vec1, vec2)`

The algorithm is detailed below, where \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}' are consistent with our aforementioned definitions 3.1, 3.2.

Algorithm 3: DMD underlying concept in modred
Medium data size (Vector space approach)

```

// Measure and define time-equidistant snapshots
1  $\mathbf{x}_i$  for  $i = 0, \dots, n$ 
// Compute each entry of the correlation matrix
2  $\mathbf{H}_{ij} = \langle \mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j \rangle$ , for  $i, j = 0, \dots, n - 1$ , hence using all but the last
available snapshot
// Eigendecomposition (=> Corollary 9.1) sorted descending
3  $\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{\Sigma} = \text{eig}(\mathbf{H})$ 
// Construct left singular vectors/ POD modes
4  $\phi_j = \sum_{i=0}^n \mathbf{x}_i [\mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1/2}]_{i,j}$ 
// Define sub-matrix  $\mathbf{H}'$ , i.e.  $\mathbf{H}$  with the first column removed
5  $\mathbf{H}' = [\mathbf{H}]_{0:n-1,1:n-1}$ 
// Compute correlation with last snapshot/ remaining last column of
the complete correlation matrix
6  $\mathbf{h}_{nj} = \langle \mathbf{x}_j, \mathbf{x}_n \rangle$  for  $j = 0, \dots, n - 1$ 
// Compute operator  $\mathbf{M}$  (analogous to  $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$  in step 2 of the DMD via SVD)
7 Compute  $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1/2} \mathbf{U}^* [\mathbf{H}', \mathbf{h}_n] \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1/2}$ 
// Compute eigendecomposition of  $\mathbf{M}$  (analogous to step 3 of the DMD
via SVD)
8  $\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{\Lambda} = \text{eig}(\mathbf{M})$ 
// Derive unscaled DMD modes as an intermediate result
9  $\tilde{\varphi}_j = \sum_{i=0}^n \phi_j [\mathbf{V}]_{i,j}$ 
// Intermediate step - scaling factors
10  $\mathbf{d}' := [\mathbf{d}]_i = \langle \tilde{\varphi}_i, \mathbf{x}_0 \rangle$ 
// Computation of the vector containing the scaling factors
11  $\mathbf{d} = (\mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{V})^{-1} \mathbf{d}'$ 
// Scaling of the DMD modes
12  $\varphi_i = [\mathbf{d}]_i \tilde{\varphi}_i$ 

```

Algorithm 3 has been simplified in steps 2,5,9,10,12 in terms of combined or eliminated computations (for more details cf. [1]) which might reduce the execution time. It is outlined in the following.

Algorithm 4: DMD implementation modred
Medium (Vector space approach)

```

// Measure and define time-equidistant snapshots
1  $\mathbf{x}_i$  for  $i = 0, \dots, n$ 
// Compute each entry of the correlation matrix
2  $\mathbf{H}_{ij} = \langle \mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j \rangle$ , for  $i, j = 0, \dots, n - 1$ , hence using all but the last
available snapshot
// Eigendecomposition (=> Corollary 9.1) sorted descending
3  $\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{\Sigma} = \text{eig}(\mathbf{H})$ 
// Define sub-matrix  $\mathbf{H}'$ , i.e.  $\mathbf{H}$  with the first column removed
// Compute correlation with last snapshot/ remaining last column of
the complete correlation matrix
4  $\mathbf{h}_{nj} = \langle \mathbf{x}_j, \mathbf{x}_n \rangle$  for  $j = 0, \dots, n - 1$ 
// Compute operator  $\mathbf{M}$  (analogous to  $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$  in step 2 of the DMD via SVD)
5 Compute  $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1/2} \mathbf{U}^* [\mathbf{H}', \mathbf{h}_n] \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1/2}$ 
6  $\mathbf{H}' = [\mathbf{H}]_{0:n-1, 1:n-1}$ 
7 Use results of  $\mathbf{H}$  and compute the remaining correlation column  $\mathbf{h}_n$  via
 $\mathbf{h}_{nj} = \langle \mathbf{x}_n, \mathbf{x}_j \rangle$  for  $j = 0, \dots, n - 1$ 
// Compute operator  $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$  (Step 3 DMD SVD)
8 Compute  $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1/2} \mathbf{U}^* [\mathbf{H}', \mathbf{h}_n] \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1/2}$ 
9  $\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{\Lambda} = \text{eig}(\mathbf{M})$  //  $\lambda_i = \text{Ritz values}$ 
// Compute coefficient matrix  $\mathbf{T}$ 
10  $\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1/2} \mathbf{V} \mathbf{D}$  where  $\mathbf{D}$  is a diagonal matrix with diagonal
 $\mathbf{d} = (\mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{V})^{-1} \mathbf{V}^* \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1/2} \mathbf{U}^* \mathbf{H}_{[0:n-1, 1]}$ 
// Construction of DMD modes
11  $\varphi_j = \sum_{i=0}^n \mathbf{x}_i [\mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{x}}]_{i,j}$ 

```

Translated to code this results in

```

DMD = modred.DMDHandles(inner_product)
ritz_vals, mode_norms_squared, build_coeffs = DMD.compute_decomp(vec_handles)
DMD.compute_modes(range(10), mode_handles)

```

where `ritz_vals` correspond to the approximative eigenvalues (Ritz values) λ_i , `mode_norms_squared` to $\|\varphi_i\|^2$ and `build_coeffs` to \mathbf{T} . They are all returned as numpy-arrays.

The function calls highlights the object-oriented structure of `modred`.

Moreover, it enables its user to integrate pre-compiled code in languages such as C/C++ or Fortran, such that performance restrictions set by Python might be mainly defied. Within that context, one may consider associated software

packages such as Cython², SWIG³ or f2py⁴.

4.1.1 Parallelization

The parallelization scheme of `modred` is identical for all modal decompositions and can be divided into two different sections within the software progress, i.e. the computation of

1. Inner product matrices / Correlation matrices
2. Linear combinations

Inner product matrices/ Correlation matrices Such step is stated by `modred` to be the presumably most expensive one. This step is parallelizable, as the whole inner product matrix (in case of the DMD equivalent to the correlation matrix $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X}$) is as aforementioned by construction composed out of inner products. Hence, for each element of the matrix, only 2 vectors are required simultaneously, i.e.

$$\mathbf{H}_{ij} = \langle \mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{x}_j \rangle \quad (4.2)$$

Note that in the case of the DMD and \mathbf{z}_i would correspond to \mathbf{x}_i . We however decide to stick with the general notation. This is a particularly advantageous feature for large datasets, as it temporarily dissolves data dependencies, which makes this step of the algorithm favorable to distributed parallelization. In the following, n_c, n_r, n_w will indicate the number of columns, rows, workers, respectively. n_v defines the amount of vectors which simultaneously fit in the memory of a single worker

The first step of the parallelization scheme is the

1. **Assignment of the task area** for each process

This results into the cyclic allocation of a compact subsection of column-/rows of \mathbf{H} which should be computed by the corresponding worker. One constructs almost evenly sized data chunks of size $b_r = n_r/n_w$, $b_c = n_c/n_w$ rows, columns respectively, which constitute the task area of the corresponding worker. Hence, the first b_r rows and b_c columns are tackled by the first process, the second b_r rows and b_c columns by the second, etc.. As these data chunks might exceed the number of simultaneously storable vectors n_v , `modred` loads them as needed. Even more restrictive, the maximum size of a subset is defined as $n_v - 2$ vectors. The additional constraint of two origins in two additional reservations made. On the one hand for the reservation of MPI buffers corresponding to the Send/Receive operation, on the other for

²C-Extensions for Python

³Simplified Wrapper and Interface Generator (Tailored for C/C++)

⁴Fortran to Python interface generator

the second vector of the inner product.
Precisely, the (pseudo)code for each worker is given as

Algorithm 5: Implementation modred
(Parallelization inner product matrices)

```

// Iterate over subset of modes
1 for i = 1 to nr/((nw)(nv - 2)) do
2   Load vectors zi corresponding to current row subset
3   for j = 1 to nv - 1 do
4     Load a single column xj into memory
5     // First iteration
6     if j == 1 then
7       Hij = ⟨zi, xj⟩
8     // Compute inner products
9     for w = 1 to nw do
10      // Communication point
11      Exchange (send and receive) xj with every other process in a
12      circular pattern
13      Hij = ⟨zi, xj⟩
14
15 // Every worker has a different chunk of H
16 // Synchronization over all processes => complete matrix
17 allreduce operation over H

```

According to modred [1], this parallelization section scales linearly with the number of workers n_w . The number of loads, which are often the most crucial fraction regarding performance, scale quadratically with n_w and correspond to the number of columns n_c . The quadratic behavior originates in the aspect that the number of loads decreases with the rise of available processes. Hence, even if $n_r > n_c$, modred chooses to transpose the vectors/snapshots to fully capitalize the scaling behaviour.

The overall complexity boundaries are summarized in the following table

Operation	Complexity
Loads	$O\left(\frac{n_c n_r}{n_v n_w^2}\right) + O\left(\frac{n_r}{n_w}\right)$
Send-receives	$O\left(\frac{n_c n_r}{n_v n_w}\right)$
Inner products	$O\left(\frac{n_c n_r}{n_w}\right)$

Even more, as for the DMD the inner product matrix constitutes the correlation matrix, which is symmetric by construction, the computation of one triangle of the matrix suffices, leading to a bisection of the inner product computations.

Having discussed the first parallelized section of modred, one may approach

the second, i.e.

Linear combinations / modes Such aims to derive the modes out of the given snapshots resulting in

$$\varphi_j = \sum_i [\mathbf{T}]_{i,j} \mathbf{x}_i, \quad j = 1, \dots, r \quad (4.3)$$

hence a linear combination with coefficient matrix \mathbf{T} as previously outlined. Again, we begin the discussion of the second parallelized code fragment within `modred` with the derivation of some terminology. Concretely, we define n_s, n_m as the number of snapshots, modes respectively. Analogously to the parallelization scheme of the correlation matrix, the first step is the **assignment of the task area** for each process. Within this context, this corresponds to the division of snapshots and modes (, where the latter still need to be computed). Again, we divide them as evenly as possible such that $b_s = n_s/n_w, b_m = n_m/n_w$ are assigned in a cyclic manner to each process.

Algorithm 6: Implementation `modred`
Parallelization linear combinations (modes)

```

// Initial assignment of task area for each worker
1 Definition of  $b_s, b_m$  for each worker
// Iterate over subset of modes
2 for  $i = 1$  to  $n_v - 2$  do
    // Iterate over own task area
    3 for  $j = 1$  to  $n_s/n_w$  do
    4     Load one snapshot  $\mathbf{x}_j$  corresponding to own task area
        // Sum up snapshots for modes
    5     for  $w = 1$  to  $n_w$  do
        // First fraction of mode
    6         if  $w = 1$  then
    7              $\varphi_i = \mathbf{x}_i[\mathbf{T}]_{i,j}$ 
    8         else
        // Communication point
    9             Exchange (send and receive) own snapshot  $\mathbf{x}_j$  with every
                other process in a circular pattern
    10             $\varphi_i = \varphi_i + \mathbf{x}_i[\mathbf{T}]_{i,j}$ 
        // Each worker has a complete mode subset
    11     Save the complete mode subset to disk (and start computation
        of new one in the next iteration of  $i$ )

```

The complexity of the second part of the parallelization is very similar to its predecessor's. Again, in general, we observe *linear* scaling with n_w , but

quadratic scaling regarding the loads (for the same connection to the number of workers). Analogously to the inner product matrices, the overall complexity boundaries are summarized in the following table and in figure 4.1.

Operation	Complexity
Loads	$O\left(\frac{n_s n_m}{n_v n_w^2}\right)$
Send-receives	$O\left(\frac{n_s n_m}{n_v n_w}\right)$
Scalar multiplications	$O\left(\frac{n_s n_m}{n_w}\right)$

(a) Inner products.

(b) Linear combinations.

Figure 4.1: Scaling on the example of a quadratic matrix with $n_r = n_c = 8000$ with a maximum number of vectors in memory of $n_v = 5$ [8]. Speedup is defined as $S_p = \frac{T_1}{T_p}$, where T_p defines the execution time on p processes [7].

As a further optimization, one might also integrate a *Hybrid* parallelization approach in *modred*. In this sense, one might simultaneously exploit a shared architecture parallelization strategy, e.g. via OpenMP, in the step of data loading and storage. Precisely, the user may define the passed handles, respectively the underlying implementation for these operations in such parallelized manner. Handles are required in *modred* due to their object oriented software paradigm, enfavoring generalized and modular approaches [1].

Having discussed a *parallel* approach towards the DMD implementation on the example of *modred*, we may devote ourselves to a varying, more mathematically driven, technique, which will be presented in the following.

4.2 Randomized - Ristretto

With the rise of *Big Data* not only parallel computing yielded further attention, but also a new direction of computational linear algebra emerged, precisely,

the field of *randomized linear algebra*.

Hence, upfront pondering if and how one could capitalize such also with respect to the Dynamic Mode Decomposition, let us quickly introduce some of its general main concepts.

4.2.1 Randomized Linear Algebra

The core objective constitutes the derivation of a smaller representation of a (high-dimensional) matrix \mathbf{X} , which is also often referred to as a *sketch*. The manner of how such may be computed, is hereby divided into two fields, i.e.

1. Random Sampling
2. Random Projection

where the names of each reveal the coarse-grained classified technique.

Both techniques perform the reduction by choosing a "random" set of rows or columns. Whereas the manner of the first is a simple sampling, the second relies on the projection onto a lower-dimensional space. One may remark, that in practice, "random" is often more or less equivalent to "interesting". Once again, such term may be diversely defined depending on the given context and application. Hence, the crux of this technique is the decision about which of the rows one may deem to be "interesting". In practice, some common heuristics constitute various forms of energy-based ranking, which may be e.g. evaluated via the cumulative sum of the singular values. Other techniques relying on this characteristic are given by leverage-scores and length-squared samplings, which however, won't be outlined more specifically.

Generally speaking, even though random sampling tends to be superior regarding computational efficiency, random projection presumably encaptures a higher amount of accuracy. A technique which aims to interweave both is given by the *Probabilistic Framework*.

Probabilistic Framework One may divide the concept of such into two main stages

1. **Stage A** - *Derivation of a near-optimal orthonormal basis $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times t}$ for a given target rank t .*
2. **Stage B** - *Projection onto that space to obtain a low-dimensional model $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{C}^{t \times n}$ and derivation of the desired approximation within that space.*

We will approach both stages separately.

Stage A – Orthonormal basis \mathbf{Q}

Having determined a target rank t , one aims to choose \mathbf{Q} such that

$$\mathbf{X} \approx \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{Q}^*\mathbf{X} \quad (4.4)$$

for $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n}$. To put it differently, the goal is to sample the column space of \mathbf{X} as optimal as possible. To compute such basis, one randomly samples such over

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{\Omega} \quad (4.5)$$

where $\mathbf{\Omega} \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times t}$ constitutes a random test matrix drawn from a Gaussian distribution. Unfortunately, though reasonable in theory, this matrix multiplication might be quite expensive in case of dense systems. More concretely, the complexity is in $O(mnt)$. As a result, in practice, one often relies on other matrix formats such as the randomized Hadamard transform⁵, which we however won't discuss any further.

The final step to obtain the unitary matrix, is the computation of a QR decomposition such that

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{R} \quad (4.6)$$

Stage B – Low-dimensional projection \mathbf{B}

As one may now assume that with high probability the column space of \mathbf{X} may be encapsured even within a low-dimensional space, we will project it onto it, such that

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{Q}^*\mathbf{X} \quad (4.7)$$

where one may note that $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{C}^{t \times n}$ is much smaller than the original matrix $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n}$. However, as already explained in the DMD-SVD approach, one may reproject the results back to the high-dimensional space, via a left-multiplication with the matrix \mathbf{Q} , as

$$\mathbf{X} \approx \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{B} \quad (4.8)$$

Due to this *stochastically* driven context, one may conclude already, that the success of such may vary depending on the given context. Hence, one may decide to interweave further optimization techniques, which may be quickly outlined below.

⁵The application of such results into a complexity reduction to $O(mn \log(t))$

Oversampling As discussed within the course of the singular value decomposition in section 3.2, the resulting left singular vector matrix \mathbf{U}_t would provide the best possible basis for the column space of rank t according to the Eckhart-Young Theorem 9. However, as often t is chosen to be smaller than the actual rank, one may truncate fractions which do influence the system. Hence, it is common to sample a few p (usually $\in \{5, 10\}$) more columns to improve the basis by increasing the probability of encapturing the desired rank. This results into $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times l}$, $\mathbf{\Omega} \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times l}$ where $l = t + p$.

Power iterations This technique is especially beneficial if the spectrum of singular values slowly decays. As this means, that the data is bounded to a large variance, this affects the probability that the *random* sampling of the column space will be successful and sufficiently accurate. Hence, to avoid such behavior and improve the quality of results, one may decide to preprocess the matrix \mathbf{X} and obtain the modified projection as

$$\mathbf{Y} = ((\mathbf{X}\mathbf{X}^*)^q \mathbf{X})\mathbf{\Omega} \quad (4.9)$$

where q defines the number of power iterations.

The efficacy of such technique becomes clear if one once again considers the SVD of $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^*$ and realizes that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{X}^q &:= (\mathbf{X}\mathbf{X}^*)^q \\ &= ((\mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^*)(\mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^*)^*)^q \mathbf{X} \\ &= (\mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}^2\mathbf{U}^*)^q \mathbf{X} \\ &= \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}^{2q}\mathbf{U}^*\mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^* \\ &= \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}^{2q+1}\mathbf{V}^* \end{aligned}$$

Nevertheless, despite the impact of such method and the aspect that often only $q = \{1, 2\}$ iterations may suffice to significantly improve the results, one may be aware of the cost of such optimization. Precisely, for q power iterations, the matrix has to be passed q times, which, even if working in a non-distributed scenario, might become prohibitive regarding large data sets (one may be reminded that in modern HPC and hardware architectures, the largest bottleneck is memory access, instead of floating point operations [7]). As a consequence, it limits its practical relevance. Additionally, even if one would apply such technique, one would have to be particularly aware of the numerical instability, as required orthogonalization steps might once again impair the resulting execution time [3, 8].

In sum, one may obtain the randomized **QB** decomposition as in the following.

Algorithm 7: Randomized QB decomposition following [8].

Input:

- $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n}$, (complete) snapshot matrix
 - t , target rank. Typically $t \ll \min(m, n)$
 - p tuning parameter (oversampling): number of additional samples
 - q tuning parameter (power iterations): number of power iterations
-

```

1  $l = t + p$ 
2  $\mathbf{\Omega} = \text{rand}(n, l)$ 
3  $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{\Omega}$  // Randomly sampled test matrix
4 for  $j=1$  to  $q$  // Optional power iterations
5 do
6    $\mathbf{Q}_{,-} = \text{qr}(\mathbf{Y})$ 
7    $\mathbf{Z}_{,-} = \text{qr}(\mathbf{X}^* \mathbf{Q}_{,-})$ 
8    $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{Z}_{,-}$ 
9  $\mathbf{Q}_{,-} = \text{qr}(\mathbf{Y})$  // Orthonormalization of  $\mathbf{Y}$ 
10  $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{Q}_{,-}^* \mathbf{X}$  // Near optimal projection onto lower-dimensional space

```

Again, as in various occasions within this thesis, we exploited the reduced cost of low-dimensional subspaces, though in contrast to the preceding manner, we herewith relied on the power of probability.

As evident, the probabilistic framework relies heavily on matrix-matrix multiplications which are particularly favorable to GPU computing. Hence, one may exploit such characteristic to accelerate the computation with ease.

4.2.2 Randomized DMD - ristretto

Coming back to the subject of this thesis, the idea of *sketching* a matrix might also be applied to the Dynamic Mode Decomposition. Precisely, one may approach the problem as plenty discussed by first of all projecting it into a lower dimensional subspace. Precisely, one will choose

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{\Omega}\mathbf{X}, \quad \mathbf{Y}' = \mathbf{\Omega}\mathbf{X}' \quad (4.10)$$

as a random subset of rows/samples of the given dataset, with $\mathbf{\Omega} \in \mathbb{C}^{l \times n}$ as the random test matrix (e.g. out of a Gaussian distribution). Once again, one may remark, that both matrices are only formed explicitly for theoretical reasons. Additionally, to prevent unnecessary confusion, we will introduce the subscript notation \mathbf{X}_C to make clear that we are operating on the complete set of snapshots, hence $\mathbf{X}_C \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n+1}$. With that in mind, we will further conclude our analysis.

Precisely, the drawback to the presented first step may become clear, considering the dependency on the chosen rank l , regardless of the real intrinsic rank r . This motivates a varying approach.

First of all, following the previously discussed probabilistic framework, one may compute a near-optimal basis $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times l}$ and projects the data onto it, such that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{b}_0, \mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_{n+1} &:= \mathbf{Q}^* \mathbf{x}_0, \dots, \mathbf{Q}^* \mathbf{x}_{n+1} \in \mathbb{C}^l \\ &\Leftrightarrow \\ \mathbf{B}_C &:= \mathbf{Q}^* \mathbf{X}_C \end{aligned} \quad (4.11)$$

which we analogously to \mathbf{X}_C divide into

$$\mathbf{B} = \left[\begin{array}{c|c|c} | & | & | \\ \mathbf{x}_0 & \mathbf{x}_1 & \dots \dots \mathbf{x}_{n-1} \\ | & | & | \end{array} \right], \quad \mathbf{B}' = \left[\begin{array}{c|c|c} | & | & | \\ \mathbf{x}_1 & \mathbf{x}_1 & \dots \dots \mathbf{x}_n \\ | & | & | \end{array} \right], \quad (4.12)$$

with $\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{B}' \in \mathbb{C}^{l \times n}$ hence l randomly optimally sampled rows. Within that lower dimensional space, we aim to attain an optimal linear least-squares relation between these two sequences, which maps \mathbf{B} to \mathbf{B}' , leading to the optimization problem

$$\hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\mathbf{B}} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{B}}} \|\mathbf{B}' - \mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{B}\|_F^2 \quad (4.13)$$

Such problem occurred various times within this thesis and may be analogously solved via the pseudoinverse \mathbf{B}^\dagger of \mathbf{B} leading to

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\mathbf{B}} &:= \mathbf{B}' \mathbf{B}^\dagger \\ &= \mathbf{B}' \tilde{\mathbf{V}} \tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{U}}^* \end{aligned} \quad (4.14)$$

with $\tilde{\mathbf{U}}^* \in \mathbb{C}^{l \times t}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{V}} \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times t}$, $\tilde{\Sigma} \in \mathbb{C}^{t \times t}$ denoting the truncated left and right singular vectors, respectively singular values of \mathbf{B} . Having derived the optimal linear operator $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\mathbf{B}}$ in the lower dimensional subspace, we aim to reproject it back to its high-dimensional origin in a well-known manner hence

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{\mathbf{B}} &= \tilde{\mathbf{U}}^* \hat{\mathbf{A}}_{\mathbf{B}} \tilde{\mathbf{U}} \\ &= \tilde{\mathbf{U}}^* \mathbf{B}' \tilde{\mathbf{V}} \tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (4.15)$$

Again, we endeavoured such projection onto the space spanned by the left singular vectors as they encode information about the core *spatial-temporal* structures of the system. Hence, following previous computations, we compute the eigendecomposition

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{\mathbf{B}} \tilde{\Phi}_B = \tilde{\Phi}_B \Lambda \quad (4.16)$$

Whereas the eigenvalues constitute the DMD eigenvalues of both spaces, the eigenvectors solely constitute the DMD modes of the projected space. To obtain the full high-dimensional space, we may recover such as

$$\Phi = \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{B}' \tilde{\mathbf{V}} \tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \tilde{\Phi}_B \quad (4.17)$$

Hence, we may obtain the full algorithm for the *Randomized Dynamic Mode Decomposition* as in the following [8].

Algorithm 8: Randomized DMD (rDMD) following [8]

```

1  $\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{B}_C \leftarrow$  Compute randomized QB decomposition
2  $\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{B}' \leftarrow$  Divide the projected dataset  $\mathbf{B}_C$  into two overlapping subsets
3  $\mathbf{B} \approx \tilde{\mathbf{U}}, \tilde{\Sigma}, \tilde{\mathbf{V}}$  // Compute the TSVD on  $\mathbf{B}$ 
4  $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_B = \tilde{\mathbf{U}}^* \mathbf{B}' \tilde{\mathbf{V}} \tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}$  // Optimal least-squares fit in projected space
5  $\tilde{\Phi}_B, \Lambda = \text{eig}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_B)$  // Extract spatial information & DMD eigenvalues
6  $\Phi = \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{B}' \tilde{\mathbf{V}} \tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \tilde{\Phi}_B$  // Reproject modes back to high-dimensional space
```

One may note, that this approach is exactly congruent to the DMD via SVD 2, apart from the two preliminary steps. As a result, it may be considered as some form of *preprocessing* step justifying the separation of the algorithm into two phases

1. *Preprocessing phase* (Steps 1-2)
2. *Core DMD phase* (Steps 3-6)

which we will use in the subsequent chapter. Implementations of the required steps are available e.g. over open-source randomization libraries such as `ristretto`⁶.

Having presented two approaches, one may wonder which of the kind may be deemed superior. Even more, if, and how, one might achieve an interweaving of both. We will discuss this within the next section.

4.3 Parallelization and Randomization combined

Upfront further scrutinizing a suggestion of such approach, one may be reminded, that in general, each solution must be tailored to the originating problem to attain optimal efficiency. What may seem like a trivial understanding at first, actually is of uttermost importance, particularly within the HPC context.

Pre-eminently, among many other aspects, one may consider

1. Problem size
2. Type of operation

Starting with the first factor, one must recall that with the usage of parallelization there always comes along an associated amount of *parallel overhead*, adding additional effort due to supplementary communication operations [7].

⁶GitHub: <https://github.com/erichson/ristretto>

Hence, for every problem, one may herewith evaluate with how many workers, i.e. processes, threads, etc. one may achieve the most efficient computation. If the problem is so small that the overhead exceeds the performance benefits, a resulting sequential algorithm may be absolutely justified in the same manner. However, if one finds the necessity to further follow up an optimized, distributed approach, as commonly prevalent in *Big Data* and discussed in the previous two sections, one may regard the specificity of each operation on its own. With this in mind, we will once again contemplate algorithm 8 (Randomized DMD) and the chosen separation into two phases.

The *preprocessing phase* relies on algorithm 7 (Randomized QB decomposition). Its most expensive operations constitute the QR-decompositions in step 6, 7 and 9. Fortunately, one may exploit existing parallel implementations for distributed architectures in this regard, one Helmholtz-brewed example being the open-source python library `Heat`⁷.

Nevertheless, we must be aware of additional synchronization points, necessary after the first QR decomposition in step 5 of the algorithm.

This overhead becomes particularly severe if one decides to apply power iterations. Especially in the context of *Big Data*, the author would suggest particular caution in this regard, as prohibitive costs may be raised by means of the associated dense matrix-matrix multiplications and memory access of tremendous data amounts.

Instead, one may identify further parallelization opportunities. Steps 2, i.e. the construction of the random test matrix $\mathbf{\Omega}$, may be deemed embarassingly parallelizable, as one advantage of *randomness* within this context comprises the lack of induced data dependencies. Afterwards, one may decide to construct \mathbf{Y} in parallel and gather the results once again upfront the first QR-decomposition. Subsequently, such may be computed as its successor in a distributed manner, with the intended benefit that, at this point of the algorithm, $\mathbf{X}_C \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n+1}$ is already reduced to $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times l}$. This leads to a cheaper computation of the most expensive component of the algorithm, as well as a shortened amount of memory accesses, which commonly constitute a bottleneck of their own.

A suggestion of a parallelized version of the randomized QB decomposition will be summarized in the following:

⁷Helmholtz Analytic Toolkit, GitHub: <https://github.com/helmholtz-analytics/heat>

Algorithm 9: Suggestion Parallelized Randomized QB decomposition based on [8] for distributed (or hybrid) architectures

Input:

- $\mathbf{X}_C \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n+1}$, snapshot matrix
 - t , target rank. Typically $t \ll \min(m, n)$
 - p tuning parameter (oversampling): number of additional samples
 - q tuning parameter (power iterations): number of such
-

```

1  $l = t + p$ 
2  $\Omega = \text{rand}(n + 1, l)$  // embarrassingly parallel
3  $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{X}_C \Omega$  // parallelizable
  // Synchronization point if parallized (Gather  $\mathbf{Y}$ )
  // Power iterations (opt., adivseds against)
4 for  $j=1$  to  $q$  do
5    $\mathbf{Q}_{,-} = \text{qr}(\mathbf{Y})$  // parallelizable
  // Synchronization point
6   Gather and redistribute  $\mathbf{Q}$  to all processes
7    $\mathbf{Z}_{,-} = \text{qr}(\mathbf{X}^* \mathbf{Q})$  // parallelizable
  // Synchronization point
8   Gather  $\mathbf{Z}$  on one process
9    $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{XZ}$  // parallelizable
  // Synchronization point if parallized (Gather  $\mathbf{Y}$ )
  // Orthonormalization of  $\mathbf{Y}$ 
10  $\mathbf{Q}_{,-} = \text{qr}(\mathbf{Y})$  // parallelizable
  // Projection onto lower-dimensional space
11  $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{Q}^* \mathbf{X}$  // GPU acceleration, opt.
```

Having derived the Randomized QB decomposition and the separation of \mathbf{B} into two subsets (step 2 of algorithm 7), one may approach the remaining proceeding of the algorithm.

Again, we consider each step separately and identify the most expensive fractions. In this case, they are presumably given by the singular value decomposition in step 3, as well as the eigendecomposition in step 5.

Though the author is unaware of a distributed implementation of the SVD at the time of this thesis, an optimized, (GPU) accelerated version may be constructed (e.g. see [5, 10]). For the eigendecomposition, on the contrary, some distributed implementations may be available, once again e.g. via `Heat`. With this in mind, the author provides another proposal.

Algorithm 10: Suggestion Parallelized Randomized DMD (rDMD)
based on its sequential counterpart presented by [8]

- 1 $\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{B}_C \leftarrow$ Parallel randomized QB decomposition (\rightarrow algorithm 9)
- 2 $\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{B}' \leftarrow$ Divide the projected dataset \mathbf{B}_C into two overlapping subsets
// Compute the TSVD on \mathbf{B}
- 3 $\mathbf{B} \approx \tilde{\mathbf{U}}, \tilde{\Sigma}, \tilde{\mathbf{V}}$ // (GPU) accelerated version
// Optimal l.-s.fit in projected space
- 4 $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_B = \tilde{\mathbf{U}}^* \mathbf{B}' \tilde{\mathbf{V}} \tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}$
// Extract spatial information & DMD eigenvalues
- 5 $\tilde{\Phi}_B, \Lambda = \text{eig}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_B)$ // parallelizable
// Reproject modes back to high-dimensional space
- 6 $\Phi = \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{B}' \tilde{\mathbf{V}} \tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \tilde{\Phi}_B$

In general, in both phases, it would make sense to consider an acceleration over GPU computing, due to the abundance of existing matrix-matrix multiplications, which are particularly favorable to this hardware component.

At a larger scale, to evaluate and further clarify the efficacy this suggestion of this combined variant as a whole, a more detailed analysis regarding performance and accuracy would be required and is strongly encouraged in this regard.

With this in mind, one completes the discussion of possible implementation strategies of the DMD and attains to summarize the results in the following.

5 Conclusion

We have seen that the DMD yields the potential for various applications, which motivated its further consideration in the first place.

Hence, as the initial part of its analysis, with the objective to firmly grasp the underlying problem and aspired optimal outcome, we have discussed the theory of (linear) dynamical systems with particular emphasis on its induced simplified solution theory. However, as ideal scenarios unfortunately rarely occur in practice, we approached the Koopman Mode Decomposition, as a strategy to tackle the issue of *nonlinearity*. Within such, we strived for a transformation to a Hilbert space of observables, within whom the system behaved linearly (via the Koopman operator \mathcal{K}_t). Nevertheless, despite the demonstrated effectiveness of this technique, we have concluded that its success heavily depends on the sophisticated choice of observables g_i . Precisely such, however, may be highly-nontrivial and furthermore (implicitly) induces dependency of at least partial insight into the system.

As a result, we introduced the *Dynamic Mode Decomposition* as a *data-driven* approximation technique of the Koopman Analysis and presented the two main theoretical algorithms for its computation, the Arnoldi and the SVD variant. The main challenge we herewith identified, precisely prevalent within the context of *Big Data*, was given by an efficient implementation strategy. Hence, we discussed two main directions effective in HPC, one given by a representant of *parallel distributed* computing, the other by a *randomized* approach. Last but not least, the author contemplated about a strategy to combine the efficacies of both. However, it is evident, that the evaluation of such requires a further analysis.

This falls in line with the aspect, that in general, the DMD constitutes a field of open research. However, due to the aspect, that it is nothing more than a *best fit linear regression technique*, it offers plenty of potential to extend and tailor the algorithm with all of the associated discoveries, such that a given problem may be most efficiently solved.

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